

PERCEPTIONS

UNDERSTAND THE IMPACT OF NOVEL TECHNOLOGIES, SOCIAL MEDIA, AND PERCEPTIONS IN COUNTRIES ABROAD ON MIGRATION FLOWS AND THE SECURITY OF THE EU & PROVIDE VALIDATED COUNTER APPROACHES, TOOLS AND PRACTICES

D2.3 Analysis of policies and policy recommendations

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 833870.

Project

Acronym	PERCEPTIONS
Title	Understand the Impact of Novel Technologies, Social Media, and Perceptions in Countries Abroad on Migration Flows and the Security of the EU & Provide Validated Counter Approaches, Tools and Practices
Coordinator	SYNYO GmbH
Reference	833870
Type	Research and Innovation Action (RIA)
Programme	HORIZON 2020
Topic	SU-BES01-2018 Human factors, and social, societal, and organisational aspects of border and external security
Start	01 September 2019
Duration	36 months
Website	https://project.perceptions.eu/
Consortium	<p>SYNYO GmbH (SYNYO), Austria Sheffield Hallam University (CENTRIC), UK Alma Mater Studiorum Universita di Bologna (UNIBO), Italy University of Granada (UGR), Spain University Rey Juan Carlos (URJC), Spain University of Northumbria at Newcastle (UNN), UK Swansea University (SU), UK University of Rome La Sapienza (SAPIENZA), Italy Erasmus University Rotterdam (EUR), Netherlands University of Antwerp (UANTWERPEN), Belgium International Centre for Migration Policy Development (ICMPD), Austria Kentro Meleton Asfaleias - Center for Security Studies (KEMEA), Greece Center for the Study of Democracy (CSD), Bulgaria SINUS Markt- und Sozialforschung GmbH (SINUS), Germany Centre de Recherche en Economie Appliquée pour le Développement (CREAD), Algeria Egyptian Centre for Innovation and Technology Development (ECITD), Egypt ADITESS Advanced Integrated Technology Solutions & Services LTD (ADITESS), Cyprus Association of Local Democracy Agencies (ALDA), France Kosovar Centre for Security Studies (KCSS), Kosovo Euro-Arab Foundation for Higher Studies (FUNDEA), Spain Koinonia Caritas Cyprus (CARITAS), Cyprus Fondazione Bruno Kessler (FBK), Italy Hellenic Police (HP), Greece Ministry of Public Security - Israel National Police (MOPS-INP), Israel Ministry of Interior - Chief Directorate Border Police (CDBP), Bulgaria</p>

Deliverable

Number	D2.3
Title	Analysis of policies and policy recommendations
Lead beneficiary	ICMPD
Work package	WP2
Dissemination level	Public (PU)
Nature	Report (RE)
Due date	31.03.2020
Submission date	31.03.2020
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Document history

Version	Date	Comments
0.1	15.03.2020	Submitted to project partners for review
0.2	31.03.2020	Submission of the final deliverable

Acknowledgement: This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 833870.

Disclaimer: The content of this publication is the sole responsibility of the authors, and in no way represents the view of the European Commission or its services.

Executive Summary

According to anecdotal evidence, there seems to be a link between technological advances in communication and levels of migration¹. Mobile phones and social media platforms are used by migrants, traffickers, governments and prospective migrants alike to gain access to information about countries of destinations, routes, future perspectives, and provide information on risky journeys and rights.

Assuming perceptions of Europe which hold contested images of Europe contribute to a certain extent to decisions to migrate, and in some cases to security threats – what do countries do to address these threats? This report provides an overview of underlying rationales of policies and policy measures addressing security threats that are linked with perceptions of Europe or a particular country. While this report does not assess the impact of the measures analysed, it provides a categorisation of types of measures contributing to a better understanding of the ways in which such policy measures are intended to work. Explicating the mechanisms employed and their assumptions, such analysis contributes to a better understating of how various policy measures intend to reach their goals.

A systematic literature review on perceptions of Europe and how they are linked with potential security threats, undertaken in the framework of PERCEPTIONS, found that in the relevant migration and security literature, “perceptions” as such is rarely employed. Accordingly, the literature review found that “some countries are perceived to be stepping-stones” towards others, migrants have positive/negative perceptions of Europe or migrants have what could be categorised as a “misperception of the EU”².

For the present report, policy measures operating at the intersection of managing migration and security were collected in 12 countries which, together, cover all three categories along the migration journey – countries of origin, of transit and of destination – Algeria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Egypt, Germany, Greece, Italy, Kosovo, Spain, Tunisia and the United Kingdom. In sum, policy measures which address a security threat linked with perceptions were collected in the following policy areas: asylum, irregular migration, migrant integration, return, border management, policies addressing radicalisation, policies addressing disinformation online.

One notable result is that “perceptions” (migrants have/acquire about Europe or about a particular country) are not directly addressed by policy measures, with one notable exception – information campaigns aimed at, for instance, discouraging irregular migration towards Europe. Rather, policy measures aimed at addressing a security threat, do so by aiming to change a particular migration behaviour. In so doing, underlying mechanisms of policy measures only assume a link between perceptions and the threat they intend to address.

The analysis undertaken indicates that most policy measures collected fall under one of the following situations/categories:

- 1) measures addressing particular migration flows and assuming a threat to be prevented (e.g. policies addressing certain specific types of flows either in terms of number or composition);
- 2) measures addressing a threat which is directly linked with migration and the migration industry (e.g. policies addressing trafficking in human beings; migrant smuggling);

¹ <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/bitstream/JRC111774/kjnd29060enn.pdf>

² PERCEPTIONS D2.2. Secondary analysis of studies, projects and narratives.

- 3) measures addressing perceptions linked with the decision to migrate/migration behaviour (campaigns aimed at informing potential migrants about the dangers of irregular migration/illegal border crossing)

Employed two frameworks of analysis – types of regulatory mechanisms, from the regulatory state theory, and the intervention logic from the theory of change – this report found that most mechanisms employed to address threats linked with perceptions fall under one of these categories: “command and control” and “market-based approaches”. In most of the countries under research, threats that are being addressed through legal measures (e.g. through decrees/laws changing access of certain categories of migrants to procedures or services). Another often used measure are dissuasion campaigns aimed at informing people about the dangers of irregular migration. Some campaigns do not only aim to inform prospective migrants about the risks of irregular migration, but offer information on alternatives (such as legal migration and employment opportunities in sending regions and potential countries of destination).

In sum, while this analysis found that addressing “perceptions” is not the final aim of policy measures, the link between “perceptions” and behaviour (particularly regarding the decision to migrate) is often assumed by these measures and not questioned.

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1 Introduction

According to anecdotal evidence, there seems to be a link between technological advances in communication and levels of migration³. Mobile phones and social media platforms are used by migrants, traffickers, governments and prospective migrants alike to gain access to information about countries of destinations, routes, future perspectives, and provide information on risky journeys and rights. Migrants who have arrived in host countries tend to exaggerate their financial gains and favourably portray their lives online, conveying an overly curated image of what life might be like in Europe to prospective migrants. Although this behaviour online is not unique to migrants and some social media networks are designed to promote and reward such behaviour, it remains nonetheless a contributing factor to the creation of perceptions of Europe abroad, and consequently motivating migration decisions.

Assuming perceptions of Europe which hold contested images of Europe contribute to a certain extent to decisions to migrate, and in some cases to security threats – what do countries do to address these threats? This report provides an overview of underlying rationales of policies and policy measures addressing security threats that are linked with perceptions of Europe or a particular country.

This report will provide an understanding of “perceptions” in the framework of migration-decision making as broadly an individual process, and the complementary role it plays by elaborating on existing migration decision-making models, namely the push-pull plus model and the aspirations-capabilities framework. The “securitization of migration” is employed to refer to the context of security threats linked with migration and the states’ responses through policies and policy measures. Using the “regulatory state” as a framework of analysis is therefore fitting in understanding the link and the overlaps between migration policies and security-based policy narratives. Many of the measures addressing the related security threats aim at changing migration behaviour, and are therefore analysed through an intervention logic model in the framework of the theory of change.

The general aim of this report is to provide an overview of types of measures and policy interventions aimed at addressing security threats that are linked with perceptions. Policy measures mentioned are mainly examples shedding more clarity on the measures rationale, identifying security threats from the perspective of policymakers, narratives around migration and security-related policies, and the perceptions they aim to address.

The report is structured as following. The first section clarifies the methodological approach employed and aims to offer a conceptual framing as a starting point for analysing relevant policies and policy measures. The second section presents examples of the types of policy measures identified in the 12 countries under study. The clustering of policies into migration-related policies, security-related policies and social media and ICT policies provides a structure to our understanding of the migration-security nexus and the relevance of new technologies and social media in addressing threats linked with “perceptions”. The third section is a discussion of some of the recurrent types of measures identified – along the typology suggested by the “regulatory state” framework – as addressing threats that are linked with perceptions.

³ <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/bitstream/JRC111774/kjnd29060enn.pdf>

2 Methodology

2.1 Background and Working Concepts

This report aims to offer an overview of types of policies and policy measures aimed at addressing (security) threats which are linked with perceptions of destination areas (here, perceptions either of Europe or of a particular country). For this overview, relevant are the following concepts and relations between them, for which explanations are subsequently provided in this section:

1. perceptions of destination areas as a determining factor for migration behaviour
2. aspirations and capabilities (from the aspirations-capabilities model) for explaining the working concept of perceptions of destination areas
3. drivers of migration (from the “push-pull plus” model, including their dimensions) as echelons at which policies/policy measures analysed aim to have an impact in order to influence migration behaviour
4. agency which, according to the intervention logic employed in this analysis, is assumed by policy measures aiming to address migration behaviour (by addressing/changing/influencing drivers of migration, particularly precipitating drivers and mediating drivers)

Migration scholarship and migration policy-making seem to agree that migration is a complex, multi-faceted issue. To capture various types of people’s voluntary movements, both in terms of time/space as well as legal jurisdictions, De Haas (2019) describes migration, “in terms of people moving”. He goes further and argues that, from the perspective of those moving, “[human mobility] can only be a freedom- and life-enhancing resource or ‘capability’ if people can make the actual choice to move”. In this sense, he “proposed to define human mobility as people’s capability (freedom) to choose where to live, with residential human movement (migration) as the associated outcome”⁴. Here the distinction between aspirations and capabilities is instrumental in explaining “perceptions of destination areas” as a working concept and later on in analysing particular types of policies or measures aimed at addressing threats linked with perceptions of destination areas.

“Aspirations” refers to life aspirations and to people’s “perceptions of life ‘here’ and ‘there’”, these are subjective and influenced by “broader processes of structural change”⁵. Structural forces that shape migration have been explained through the push-pull models which, however, have been critiqued for presenting migration as a single action rather than a process. To overcome this shortcoming, Van Hear, Bakewell and Long (2017⁶) propose a “push-pull plus” model. Building on the work of Richmond (1994⁷) and Van Hear (1998⁸), this model distinguishes between four types of drivers of migration: predisposing drivers, proximate drivers, precipitating drivers and mediating drivers. In short, predisposing drivers contribute to “a context in which migration is more likely” (e.g. disparities between places of origin and destination areas). Proximate drivers have a more direct effect on

⁴ De Haas, H. (2019), Paradoxes of Migration and Development. IMI, 157: 1-22. <https://www.migrationinstitute.org/publications/paradoxes-of-migration-and-development>

⁵ De Haas, H. (2019), Paradoxes of Migration and Development. IMI, 157: 1-22.

⁶ Van Hear, N., Bakewell, O. and Long, Katy (2017), Push-pull plus: reconsidering the drivers of migration.

⁷ Richmond, A. (1994), Global Apartheid: Refugees, Racism and the New World Order, New York: OUP.

⁸ Van Hear, N. (1998), New Diasporas: The Mass Exodus, Dispersal and Regrouping of Migrant Communities. London: UCL Press.

migration and manifest as economic recession in countries of origin or new economic opportunities in regions of destination. Precipitating drivers can be linked with a particular event (e.g. outbreak of a conflict, changes in political regimes) and “trigger departure, as individuals and households take decisions to move or stay put”⁹. Finally, mediating drivers refer to the infrastructure enabling mobility (e.g. quality of transport), including the migration infrastructure comprised by policies and practices in other spheres than migration policies (e.g. trade, education, agriculture etc.), migrant networks or the related factor of what was called a “culture of migration”¹⁰. In the push-pull plus model, the above-mentioned drivers operate in both areas of origin and of destination, along several dimensions with different impacts, “according to gender, age, class, language, ethnicity, religion” etc. To understand how drivers work, the following dimensions are taken into account: 1. locality (drivers centred on places of origin, areas of destinations, or that are operating transnationally), 2. scale (whether drivers operate at local/national/regional level or whether they impact the individual/household/community level), 3. selectivity (what social groups are impacted, depending on gender, age, class, ethnicity etc.), 4. duration (the timeframe of the driver, particularly with regard to precipitating drivers), 5. tractability (drives culturally embedded, e.g. migration as a duty for a younger generation). To sum up, drivers of migration are structural factors that, combined, influence migration decisions and migration processes along the above-mentioned dimensions. Policies analysed in this report, while aiming to influence migration behaviour, address some of these factors or how they manifest along these dimensions. For instance, the amendments to the Italian asylum legislations, implemented after the 2015 crisis, when Italian shores saw a dramatic increase in the arrivals of asylum seekers, aim to restrict access to procedures for asylum seekers already in Italy, but also to send a message for those considering Italy as a potential destination. In this sense, the legal amendments address the migration infrastructure as a precipitating driver in the country of destination, for a particular type of movement (asylum seekers).

The framework employed in this report, aspirations and desires are intrinsic and subjective and are influenced by structural, external conditions. Furthermore, the decision to migrate or not to migrate (manifested as migration behaviour) is an outcome “of an interplay between these drivers and agency”. To take agency also “means to be capable of exerting some degree of control over the social relations in which one is enmeshed, which in turn implies the ability to transform those social relations to some degree”¹¹. Agency in migration behaviour is an important aspect, often assumed by policy measures. This is the case even for measures aimed at addressing a type of movement which is associated with involuntary migration although not always manifested as such – trafficking in human beings. Anti-trafficking information campaigns aim at informing potential migrants about the dangers of trafficking, assuming therefore one main situation in which trafficking occurs, namely regular migration to a destination area (for the purpose of employment), where exploitation and subsequently trafficking occurs.

Aspirations and desires to migrate are influenced, on one side by the interplay of drivers, on the other side by people’s more general life understanding and imaginations of existing life conditions or quality of life in the place they currently are (and similar conditions somewhere else). In this sense, aspirations to migrate have a relational characteristic. The project *Imagining Europe from the Outside*

⁹ Van Hear, N., Bakewell, O. and Long, Katy (2017), *Push-pull plus: reconsidering the drivers of migration*

¹⁰ Idem.

¹¹ Sewell, W.H. (1992), *A Theory of Structure: Duality, Agency, and Transformation*. *American Journal of Sociology*. 98(1): 1-29. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/2781191?seq=1>

(EUMAGINE), which investigates how people in Morocco, Senegal, Turkey and Ukraine relate to the possibility of migration, found that perceptions of particular dimensions of life in Europe as opposed to life in their countries of origin influence migration aspirations:

While negative perceptions on healthcare, education, poverty reduction policies and gender relations in their own country support emigration aspirations in general, positive perceptions on life in Europe (including healthcare, education, gender relations and poverty reduction policies) support aspirations to move to Europe”.¹²

Similarly, in addition to dissatisfaction with local circumstances, other studies underline a negative correlation between life-satisfaction on the one hand, and the wish to emigrate on the other.¹³

Migration literature which refers to perceptions of an area of destination understood as a “mental image”, links it with narratives, discourses and imaginations, but also with ideas and knowledge and information about a particular aspect of that destination area. Without detailing the meaning and scope of the field of narratology and its associated subject of study – “narrative”¹⁴, for the purpose of this report, we retain that narratives are “stories with a temporal sequence of events, unfolding a plot that is populated by dramatic moments, symbols and archetypal characters that culminate in a moral to the story”¹⁵. In social and communication theory, narratives are “the principal and inescapable mode by which we experience the world”¹⁶. From this perspective, narratives are public and personal ‘stories’ that we subscribe to and that guide our behaviour (Idem). Following this view, relevant are also policy narratives on migration – strategically constructed “stories”¹⁷ which come in many forms, with an array of stakeholders, speeches, political press releases, news stories etc. and where the political environment is also relevant.

Similar to the approach employed in the EUMAGINE project, in this report, aspirations are understood as an intermediate phase between imaginations (understood here as ideas and information) and migration decision-making (manifested as migration behaviour). “One can have images about migration or potential destinations, without really aspiring to leave or to migrate. [...] While imaginations carry the basis for a motivation to migrate, aspirations refer to people’s thoughts about migration as a possible strategy for themselves”¹⁸. “The notion of migration aspirations reflects not only socially sanctioned behaviour, but also social mechanisms of diffusion: people may observe the

¹²https://ec.europa.eu/research/social-sciences/pdf/policy_briefs/policy-briefs-eumagine-01-2013_en.pdf#view=fit&pagemode=none (26.03.2020)

¹³ <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/epdf/10.1111/imig.12617>

¹⁴ Amerian, M. and Jofi, L. (2015), Key concepts and basic notes on narratology and narrative. *Scientific Journal of Review*, 4(10): 182-192.

¹⁵ Michael D. Jones and Mark K. McBeth, A Narrative Policy Framework: Clear Enough to Be Wrong?, *The Policy Studies Journal* (PSJ), Vol. 38, No 2, 2010, p. 329

¹⁶ https://books.google.at/books?id=M_lODwAAQBAJ&printsec=frontcover&hl=de#v=onepage&q&f=false

¹⁷ Boswell, C. & Geddes, A. & Scholten, P. (2011): The Role of Narratives in Migration Policy-Making: A Research Framework. *British Journal of Politics and International Relations* 13(1), pp. 1-11.

¹⁸ Timmerman, C., Heyse, P. and Van Mol, C. (2010), Conceptual and Theoretical Framework EUMAGINE Research Project. Project Paper 1. <http://www.eumagine.org/outputs/PP1%20-%20Conceptual%20and%20Theoretical%20Framework.pdf>

migratory achievements of their peers, come to see migration as a realistic prospect and develop migration aspirations”¹⁹.

For the purpose of this analysis, “migrants’ perceptions about a destination area” (either of Europe or of a particular country) refers to the ideas and information (in the sense of knowledge²⁰) migrants have about the EU or about that country. Unlike the EUMAGINE approach, where impact of discourses on perceptions considered two types of “imaginings” – the migratory project which refers to the “range of desired and desirable identities and lifestyles through which potential migrants imagine themselves” and the geographical imaginings –, for the purpose of this analysis we will refer to geographical imaginings only. We employ a similar understanding of the concept, according to which “‘geographical imaginings’ refers to the subjectivity of the human conception of locations, spaces, countries and the people inhabiting these physical spaces”²¹. This approach acknowledges “geographical imaginings” as cultural constructions which are influenced by discourses (be it popular discourses, policy discourses or through social networks). For the purpose of this analysis a broad understanding of the concept of discourse will be employed, namely “representations, practices and performances through which meanings are produced and legitimised”²².

In order to provide an overview of types of measures addressing security threats which are linked with perceptions of destination areas, additional clarifications of the concept of security threats or risks are required. With reference to what was called “securitisation of migration”, in the early 2010s, Bourbeau (2011) identified several factors that, in his view, “have recently begun to cause alarm”: “1) the notion of migration in a collective sense posing an existential threat to the security of the state and/or the society; 2) the prominence given to immigration as a security threat; and 3) its attendant effects in political practice, which have undergone significant and even startling changes”. For something (or someone) to be a security risk, three criteria must be fulfilled: the threat has to be clearly defined, that which is endangered has to be specified (the referent object of security) and there must be a link between the threat and the referent object²³. In the policy measures considered in this report one or more of these elements are only “tacitly expressed, but the link between the threat and the referent object will be underlined through the intervention logic from theory of chance (one of the frameworks for analysis employed in this report).

¹⁹ Carling, J. and Collins, F. (2017), *Aspiration, desire and drivers of migration*. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 44 (6): 909-926. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/1369183X.2017.1384134>

²⁰ For the purpose of this analysis, knowledge here is understood as propositional knowledge – which refers to gathering (accurate) information about the world or about a specific situation (e.g. accurate information about the journey to Europe or to a particular country, about the life situation in Europe or a particular country). Information and communication technologies contribute to what has been labelled as “the problem of perceptual knowledge”, since “the way things look isn’t always the way things are; appearances can be deceptive” (Pritchard, 2010: 69). In the epistemology of knowledge this argument subscribes to indirect realism, according to which “there is an objective world out there, one that is independent of our experience of it – that is the ‘realism’ part – but that we can only know this world indirectly through experience” (Idem: 77).

²¹ Timmerman, C., Heyse, P. and Van Mol, C. (2010), *Conceptual and Theoretical Framework EUMAGINE Research Project*. Project Paper 1.

²² Idem.

²³ PERCEPTIONS D2.4. List of Threats

2.2 Methodological Approach

This report suggests a categorization of policies (including policy measures and policy recommendations) that address threats/security issues, which are linked with migrants' perceptions of destination areas (either of Europe or of a particular country). In other words, the report analyses governments' actions (be it at international, federal, national, regional or local level) targeting (potential) security threats linked with migrants' perceptions of Europe or of a particular country/region. A systematic literature review on perceptions of Europe and how they are linked with potential security threats, undertaken in the framework of PERCEPTIONS, found that in the relevant migration and security literature, "perceptions" as such are rarely employed. Existing research, including policy analyses, does not employ "perceptions" as a category of practice²⁴, but, to a rather limited extent, as a category of analysis²⁵. Accordingly, "some countries are perceived to be stepping-stones" towards others, migrants have positive/negative perceptions of Europe or migrants have what could be categorised as a "misperception of the EU"²⁶

The overall aim of this report is to present types of policies (including policy measures and policy recommendations) aimed at addressing security threats which are linked with perceptions. The policies and policy measures retained for analysis had to fulfil two main criteria: they had to address both migration and a security issue. In practical terms, the following steps were considered:

- 1) The aim of a policy included in this collection is to address a threat (either threat to the public, the border or territory of a country or of a region or threat to an individual).
- 2) Furthermore, that threat has to be linked with a migration behaviour (be it referring to the decision to migrate, drivers of migrations influencing migration processes, the consequences of migration, vulnerabilities that result from migration etc.; both legal and irregular migration, as well as voluntary and forced migration were considered).
- 3) Finally, the migration behaviour considered is thought to be linked with perceptions of Europe or of a particular country.

Rather than presenting a collection of all possible policies and types of measures, this report aims to provide for a categorisation of recurring types of such policies and measures.

The current debates on migration in Europe focus on characteristics of mixed migration and of migration policies as of 2015. Taking 2015 as the starting point for collecting relevant policies enabled

²⁴ Brubaker and Cooper (2000) differentiate between "categories of social and political practice and categories of social and political analysis" (2000: 4). In their view, "category of practice [implies] a relatively sharp distinction between 'native' or 'folk' or 'lay' categories on the one hand and 'scientific' categories on the other" (Idem). In other words, categories of practice are those categories used in policy jargon. To take an example, trafficking in human beings is both a category of practice and a category of analysis, as it is being employed in policy documents and legislation, as well as in scientific analyses. On the other hand, the term "modern slavery" is a category of practice as it is employed in policy documents (e.g. in the UK anti-trafficking legislation), but has been contested as a category of analysis for at least two reasons; first, it is an umbrella term which implies, for political reasons, that trafficking in human beings is a continuation of the transatlantic slave trade; second, the term "modern slavery", unlike trafficking in human beings, has no internationally accepted definition which adds to the difficulties when it comes to its operationalisation. For a historical perspective on this particular distinction, see Norbert Cyrus (2015), *The Concept of Demand in Relation to THB: A review of debates since the late 19th century*. DemandAT Working Paper.

²⁵ <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1023/A:1007068714468#citeas>

²⁶ PERCEPTIONS D2.2. Secondary analysis of studies, projects and narratives.

us to present recent policies and policy measures, but limited the scope of our findings, particularly for types of policies which might not fall under our categorisation.

This analysis does not challenge the link between movement/narrative/perception of a destination area and the threat which is addressed by the policies and policy measures showcased in this paper. The aim is to explicate their underlying mechanisms for achieving their declared/assumed goals. In so doing, the linkages between migration behaviour, narratives/perceptions influencing this behaviour on the one hand and the security threats on the other is being presented. In this sense, the analysis offered is descriptive and not normative, as it offers a starting analytical point for the upcoming field work in the countries/regions under study.

Policies which have been in place or implemented as of 2015 in countries under study were collected by PERCEPTIONS partners, all with long-standing experience in conducting social science research²⁷. Countries under research are both EU MS and partner countries and together cover all three categories along the migration journey – countries of origin, of transit and of destination – Algeria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Egypt, Germany, Greece, Italy, Kosovo, Spain, Tunisia and the United Kingdom. Data collection was carried out in the following languages: Albanian, Arabic, Bulgarian, English, Flemish, French, German, Greek, Italian and Spanish.

For each entry, the following was collected:

- 1) Level of the Organisation/Institution releasing the policy document (EU-, federal-, national-, regional- and local-level)
- 2) Type of policy (National Strategy, National Action Plan, White Paper, recommendations by non-governmental actors, including legislation etc.)
- 3) Year in which the policy was released and years in which the policy was implemented
- 4) Organisation/Institution issuing the policy and organisation/Institution(s) implementing the policy
- 5) Background of the policy document (Why the policy was initiated, who supported the policy, what was the initial goal of the policy, if available).
- 6) Explanation of the link with perceptions or particular narratives (It is about preventing counter-narratives, it is about repairing damage resulting from (mis)perception, it is aimed at improving social cohesion, countering security threats etc).
- 7) Final declared goal of the Policy (e.g. social cohesion, countering security threats etc.)
- 8) Main approach (what types of action is suggested - e.g. command and control, peer pressure, by design, combined approaches etc. - intervention logic, for NAPs)
- 9) Monitoring and evaluation measures foreseen in the policy document (e.g. Action Plan, Implementation Plan)
- 10) Results of concluded monitoring and evaluations (Has it been evaluated as successful? if yes, with what results?)

²⁷ Data on Algeria was primarily collected by PERCEPTIONS partners from the Euro-Arab Foundation for Higher Studies (FUNDEA) and the Centre de Recherche en Economie Appliquée pour le Développement (CREAD); Belgium: University of Antwerp (UANTWERPEN); Bulgaria: Center for the Study of Democracy (CSD); Egypt: Egyptian Center for Innovation and Technology Development (ECITD); Germany: Erasmus University Rotterdam (EUR); Greece and Cyprus: Kentro Meleton Asfaleias – Center for Security Studies (KEMEA); Italy: Alma Mater Studiorum Università di Bologna (UNIBO); Kosovo: Kosovar Centre for Security Studies (KCSS); Spain: University Rey Juan Carlos (URJC); Tunisia: University of Granada (UGR) and the International Centre for Migration Policy Development (ICMPD); United Kingdom: Sheffield Hallam University (CENTRIC) and Swansea University (SU).

Policy documents collected subscribed to the following areas: policies in the areas of asylum, policies addressing irregular migration, policies addressing trafficking in human beings, policies addressing border control, migrant integration policies, return policies, policies addressing terrorism and radicalisation, as well as policies addressing disinformation online. The following types of sources were collected: official documents elaborated by public administrations at national-, regional- or local-level (including strategies, action plans, legislations, official communications etc.), reports by non-governmental organisations and international organisations (including those formulating recommendations for policy-makers in the area of migration and security), public campaigns (such as information campaigns aimed at discouraging irregular migration).

In total, 230 of data sources were collected, out of which 126 were retained for analysis. The exclusion criteria included: lack of information provided for a data entry (and for which no relevant additional information – available online – was identified), data entry too old (long before 2015), data entry for a policy which does not address a threat linked with migration as such.

In order to understand how policies/policy measures retained for this analysis aim to address threats that are linked with perceptions (of destination areas) work, two frameworks of analysis are employed – the regulatory state and the intervention logic (as an integral part of theory of change). The next section introduces briefly these two frameworks.

PERCEPTIONS partners have been particularly instrumental at collecting relevant documents and sharing their knowledge of the different national, regional and local contexts. It is worthy to note that given the scope of this research, and the focus on “perceptions” as being a central concept in understanding policy responses to migration-related security threats, as well as policy and policy recommendations aimed at addressing these threats, some initial findings are worth mentioning. Among these challenges, of relevance both to the PERCEPTIONS project as well as to different policymakers and practitioners in the field, it is worth mentioning the limited number of policies, legal frameworks, as well as recommendations directly referring to “perceptions” of Europe as a relevant working concept in migration decision making, as well as a potential source of security threats to different communities. Linkages between perceptions and threats, if at all, are often assumed rather than explicitly described. This is the case for all 12 countries under study to varying degrees, including both EU and non-EU countries. In this context, particularly the role of social media and the spread of disinformation online regarding migration has been largely overlooked by policymakers, except for the case of disinformation in European elections.

2.3 Framework of Analysis

Aiming to explain the underlying mechanisms of policies (including policy measures and policy recommendations) identified, this report employs two frameworks – a typology of regulatory measures put forward by the literature on the regulatory state and the intervention logic as explained by the theory of change.

2.3.1 The Regulatory State

The framework of the “Regulatory State” (Moran, 2002²⁸) looks at how the state tries to regulate human behaviour using different types of measures. “Command and control” is a traditional tool to

²⁸<https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/british-journal-of-political-science/article/review-article-understanding-the-regulatory-state/93C2C39EE11020613CC1573C5F82F7DA>

regulate, characterised by the use of coercion. In practice, this translates into an authority (the state) imposing those being regulated to comply with certain rules. Usually the rule has attached to it a particular sanction, which has at least two main purposes – to correct noncompliance and to deter potential refusal to comply. The classic example of a command and control type of measure is the penal code. Crimes defined in the penal code have attached a sanction which is aimed at both, punishing those who committed the crime and discouraging those who might commit the crime in the future.

Alternative forms of regulating can be clustered in three main groups: market-based mechanisms, community based (peer-pressure) and design (Scott 2002 cited in Boswell and Kyambi, 2016: 4²⁹). “Market-based mechanisms” aim to steer human behaviour through taxes and subsidies, incentivising social actors to comply with a particular regulation. For instance, in particular employment sectors, companies who employ persons with disabilities might be exempt from some taxes.

“Peer-pressure” regulation uses the power of communities – if a sufficiently large number of social actors agree to act in a particular way, those who do not comply will be “named and shamed” and therefore pushed into compliance. This is, for example, done through showcasing the employee of the month in a company (in this case “name and fame” those who complied with certain rules) or naming and shaming, through public media communication, apparel companies who employ exploitative practices in their supply chains.

Finally, “design” is a more subtle way of steering behaviour – it refers to an infrastructure put in place in a particular policy area which, by design, determines a particular behaviour. Thaler and Sunstein (2008³⁰), based on research in behavioural psychology and economics, suggest that social environments can be designed in order to induce particular social behaviours. This is the case, for instance, of organ donor systems – in those systems in which donors have to opt out rather than to opt in, the rate of organ donations is higher.

It is worth mentioning that these types of measures are ideal types and each of them functions in already dynamic regulation environments. Furthermore, as the discussion chapter of this report will showcase, these regulatory mechanisms often operate in combination and not individually.

Public institutions’ governing mechanisms have been described by various frameworks – such as governance or what was called multilevel governance. However, considering the purpose of this report, the typology of policy measures put forward by the regulatory state, coupled with the intervention logic from the theory of change (introduced briefly in the following sub-section) offers clarity with regard to the underlying mechanisms of particular measures. This, in turn, offers a starting point for better understanding the role “perceptions of destination areas” might play in formulation of migration policy measures in these destination areas.

2.3.2 Intervention Logic from the Theory of Change

A common understanding of a Theory of Change in the literature on evaluation defines it as “the hypothesis about the way that a program brings about its effects” (Dhillon and Vaca, 2018: 65³¹). “A

²⁹ https://www.demandat.eu/sites/default/files/DemandAT_WP4_Boswell_Kyambi_Steering_Regulations_FINAL.pdf

³⁰ <https://yalebooks.yale.edu/book/9780300122237/nudge>

³¹ http://journals.sfu.ca/jmde/index.php/jmde_1/article/view/496/444

Theory of Change is an organisation’s hypothesis of the changes that will occur as it is utilising its strategies and activities to achieve its mission” (Dhillon and Vaca, 2018: 65). Theories of change are used in evaluation studies to assess the impact of a measure. “The intervention logic follows the assumed causal chain of intended effects of one single [measure]. It is part of a theory of change which [...] considers the interaction of the intervention logics of more than one activity pursued in one project. [...] Ideally, a theory of change is derived from problem analysis” (Cyrus and Vogel 2017: 12³²). Similar to the approach of Cyrus and Vogel (2017), this report “not analyse a problem and construct a theory of change to recommend interventions; instead [it analyses policies and policy measures] in order to reconstruct the underlying intervention logic”.

For the task at hand – to categorise policy measures aimed at addressing threats linked with perceptions – the intervention logic presents itself as a useful tool. By explicating the mechanism of a policy measure, such as the measure implemented in Belgium for fast tracking asylum applications after 2016 – when a government’s analysis of migration influx in Belgium revealed that the country is facing an excessive number of multiple asylum applications (under different assumed name) – intended and unintended results can be looked into. Although assessing the effects of the measures identified falls beyond the scope of this report, analysing their underlying mechanisms offers a starting point for understating the kind of impact these measures might have.

2.4 Reflection on the Framework of Analysis and the Working Concepts

With regard to the analysis undertaken in this report, some clarification on the general approach is useful. This report makes use of concepts and refers to migration (either as a field of research or as a policy area) from at least two registries of knowledge on migration. First, for conceptual clarity, the report refers to recent migration scholarship which aims at better understanding migration, so it refers to results of what was called “a theoretical mission to better understand the forces and frictions through which migration comes about and is experienced” (Carling and Collins, 2017: 909). This first registry refers to migration theory from which the working concepts of this report will draw, particularly for explaining the understanding of “perceptions of destination areas”.

Second, the report describes the underlying logic of policy measures aimed to address threats that are linked with migration behaviour.

The difference between the two registries is that while the first attempts to achieve clarity with regard to understanding migration as a phenomenon, the second attempts to reach a specific goal (e.g. attract highly-skilled, deter irregular migration etc.). While the two registers inform each-other and contribute to what was called the “reflexive-dynamics of knowledge transfer”³³, contributing to the co-production of knowledge in the area of migration, it is worth noting the two registries’ different goals. This analysis is situated somewhere in-between, as it draws on concepts from migration theory, particularly on the recent work of Carling and Collins (2017), De Haas (2019) and Van Hear, Bakewell and Long (2017) and aims to contribute to a better understanding of particular migration policy measures, contributing to

³² https://www.demandat.eu/sites/default/files/DemandAT_WP9_Cyrus-Vogel_Campaigns_June%202017.pdf

³³ The concept was elaborated in a series of workshops on the challenges of commissioned research co-organized by one of the authors of this report in 2015 and 2016 in the framework of the Annual IMISCOE Conference. Participants were both

the further goal of PERCEPTIONS project to support migration policy-makers and practitioners in their daily work³⁴.

To sum up, for the purpose of this analysis, “perceptions” refers to ideas and information which migrants have/acquire about Europe or about various countries under study – either as potential countries of destination or countries of transit, While the EUMAGINE project conceptualises Europe in terms of democracy and human rights, the method employed in this report takes an exploratory view on Europe and a particular country as destination areas. In this sense, the ideas and information that migrants have with regard to life in Europe/in countries under research can refer to a variety of aspects, such as: healthcare, education, housing, labour market, level of public security, social security or standards of living in general.

By looking into the types of policies and policies measures aimed at addressing threats which are linked with perceptions the report contributes to addressing a series of additional questions. How can one explain/understand the connections between threats (as identified by policies and policy measures) and perceptions (of Europe/ of a particular transit or destination country) that are linked with migration behaviour (an expression of human mobility)? Do policies addressing threats aim/claim to address external structural elements shaping the decision space for those considering migration? Although this report does not provide definitive answers to any of these questions, the analysis undertaken seems to indicate is that most policy measures collected fall under one of the following situations/categories:

- 1) measures addressing particular migration flows and assuming a threat to be prevented (e.g. policies addressing certain specific types of flows either in terms of number or composition)
- 2) measures addressing a threat which is directly linked with migration and the migration industry (e.g. policies addressing trafficking in human beings; migrant smuggling)
- 3) measures addressing perceptions linked with the decision to migrate/migration behaviour (campaigns aimed at informing potential migrants about the dangers of irregular migration/illegal border crossing)

This link between perceptions of destination areas, as understood in this report, and migration behaviour will be further explained in the discussion chapter of this report. Before that, the next chapter summarises the measures identified in countries under research and retained for analysis.

³⁴ See the overall aim of PERCEPTIONS.

3 Analysis of Policies and Policy Recommendations

The following gives an overview of the types of policies identified in the countries under study. The clustering of policies into migration-related policies, security-related policies and social media and ICT policies provides a structure to our understanding of the migration-security nexus and the relevance of new technologies and social media in addressing threats linked with “perceptions”. Migration-related policies are seen as policies departing from various migration areas such as asylum, integration, return, irregular migration, border management, and anti-trafficking in human beings.

Migration-related policies aim to regulate particular aspects of the migration journey, migrants’ status and stay in countries of transit and destination. With the ever-rising securitization of migration following the 2015 “Migration Crisis”³⁵, migration-related policies have increasingly expanded in scope, reflecting security concerns stemming from migration movements, and more directly addressing arising threats, both potential and present. Security-related policies are not specific to migrant populations but have increasingly addressed security threats linked with migration movements, or that tend to affect disproportionately individuals with migration backgrounds. Finally, we look at technology and social media policies as both a factor and a link to investigate the extent to which policies take into account the role of emerging technologies and social media in informing decisions to migrate and mitigate security threats linked to the use or misuse of technologies. Since the evidence on technology-driven migration and security threats in relation to perceptions is rather limited and, for the time being anecdotal, this report will look more broadly at policies addressing misinformation, policies governing the use of social media and new technologies, and the role of information campaigns, particularly in relation to social media, in addressing security threats linked with migration behaviour.

Although these clusters aim at providing a structured overview of the types of policies, policy measures and recommendations addressing security threats linked to perceptions, there is a clear overlap between some subcategories within these clusters, particularly in the area of human trafficking, seen both from a migration lens as well as a security one.

The policies outlined in the following sections are not meant to provide an exhaustive overview of all existing policies in countries under study but rather display examples of measures in countries under study, highlighting the threats identified by various policies, and the types of measures taken to counter them.

3.1 Migration-Related Policies

The following section gives an overview of migration-related policies aimed at countering security threats arising from misperceptions linked with migration. These misperceptions are explored from a policy-making perspective, framed in a context of a threat, both potential and present, along with the policy measures to counter them. Potential and present threats are intertwined with different policy narratives, which in turn, refer, to various extents, to a perception of Europe that is seen as problematic from a security perspective. This section will not evaluate these perceptions or threats but rather aims to understand the link between all these elements from a policy-making standpoint. More specifically,

³⁵ <http://www.mixedmigration.org/articles/the-ever-rising-securitisation-of-mixed-migration/>

this section will provide a typology of policies targeting asylum from 2015 onwards, as well as policies on addressing irregular migration, border control, return, integration, and human trafficking.

3.1.1 Policies in the Area of Asylum

Following the 2015 “policy migration crisis”, and the subsequent changes witnessed in Europe and its neighbouring countries, the need to reconsider migration policies became a priority for many governments and institutions. Many reforms were also motivated by pre-existing and newly arising threats, whether potential or present, as well as migrants’ perceptions of countries of asylum. Policy documents analysed in the section echo some of the threats outlined by different European as well as non-European governments.

Terms such as “disproportionate” number of asylum seekers highlights the underlying impression of governments that large influx of migrants represent a threat to countries’ stability and capacity to host asylum seekers. Documents also referred to addressing abusive practices introduced by asylum seekers who do not have a legitimate protection claim, practices which have been labelled as representing a threat to governments’ resources, taking away from the public budget and other legitimate asylum seekers. Beyond addressing the economic threats created by the strain on resources and public budgets, and the “false” claims introduced by asylum seekers, threats undermining a country’s sovereignty have also been highlighted in several policy documents, both in European and non-European countries. These threats are seen as symbolic, and call for countering measures.

In order to counter these threats, several countries introduced measures aimed at lowering unnecessary costs linked with processing asylum claims by introducing measures aimed at speeding the processing of claims, countering the abusive practices of some asylum seekers to lengthen the processing time, and by extension the individual benefits received during the waiting phase, as well as supporting the Reform of the Dublin Mechanism, which would lower the number of asylum claims introduced through secondary movements.

In Belgium, the Policy Note from the State Secretary of Asylum and Migration for 2017-2018³⁶ revealed that in 2016, an excessive number of multiple asylum applications, sometimes under different aliases, were submitted. This was largely seen as undermining the state, leading to high administrative costs and longer processing times of the initial asylum claims, and postponing the return of rejected asylum seekers. The Note underlined that asylum seekers who abusively submit multiple asylum claims do not aim to secure a refugee status or international protection, but are, for the most part, “false” asylum seekers whose goal is to extend their right to stay and work and obtain a temporary residence permit to protect them from expulsion while awaiting an asylum decision. To counter this abuse, the Policy Note advised for a faster procedure to shorten the right to stay associated with multiple asylum claims submitted, which will in turn lower the overall recourse to submitting multiple asylum claims. In some cases, rejected asylum seekers used to resubmit their asylum claim in another language, which is referred to as “linguistic shopping”. This approach was used in the hope that applications might be successful if presented in another language or that disqualifying factors from earlier asylum applications will be overlooked. This approach is no longer allowed under the Belgian Asylum Law. These measures were created to counter the economic and symbolic threats to the asylum system by

³⁶ <https://www.dekamer.be/doc/FLWB/pdf/54/2708/54K2708017.pdf>

introducing stricter measures, and limiting incentives and, by extension, changing asylum seekers' behaviours.

A similar approach was also introduced in Germany to counter the introduction of false claims of asylum and international protection and the associated costs and risks³⁷. In October 2015, the Act to Accelerate Asylum Procedures was introduced, opening the way for a new categorization of asylum applications, between applications with a high probability of being recognized as in need of international protection or refugee and others as less or not likely to be recognised. The nationality of the applicant was the basis for this categorization, which then informs subsequent decisions in the asylum process such as accommodation, access to integration courses, and obtaining a work permit. More specifically, the Act allowed to speed up asylum procedures, ensured the accommodation of both asylum seekers awaiting a decision and refugees, simplified the enforceable return of rejected asylum seekers with the objective of reducing the "false incentives" of unjustified asylum claims as well as improved the integration outcomes of those with a higher likelihood of being accepted and remaining in Germany. The Act aimed at reducing the incentive of unjustified applications by replacing cash benefits with in-kind benefits during the initial reception phase, reducing the benefits for those who have to leave the country, and excluding asylum seekers from safe countries of origin from employment. In return, integration measures supported those with "good chances of remaining" with integration courses, job-related language support, measures actively promoting employment and temporarily lifting the exclusion from the German labour market. This coupled approach, favouring specific groups of asylum seekers by providing incentives for integration and creating financial disincentives for groups posing threats to the asylum system, such as limiting benefits and access to the labour market, shows a similar pattern of altering behaviours of asylum seekers, both current and potential, through signalling and implementing stricter regulations.

In predominantly transit countries at the external border of the EU such as Greece and Cyprus, the threat of disproportionate influx of asylum seekers and the strain it poses on public budgets and government resources led to a different approach, known as the creation of hot spots and the involvement of law enforcement in asylum procedures. Following the EU-Turkey statement, "hotspots" on the Greek Aegean islands were transformed from screening centers to detention facilities, and Greece transitioned from a country of transit to a country of destination³⁸. To accommodate the changes witnessed, Greece concluded reforms to its Asylum Police, which established an Asylum Service to assess international protection claims, as well as an Appeals Committee and a First Reception Service. Registration with the Hellenic Police on arrival is a necessary step to be able to submit an asylum application.

In addition, a hotspot approach was introduced by the European Commission to support frontline member states, amongst which Greece, to alleviate the pressure and provide operational assistance to identify, register, fingerprint, and debrief newly arriving migrants and asylum seekers, as well as support return operations. Following the EU-Turkey Statement, the fast track border procedure was implemented targeting asylum seekers arriving after 20 March 2016. This procedure transformed the hotspots into closed detention centers. The registration of asylum applications and the notification of

³⁷ https://www.academia.edu/39746749/Border_Management_and_Migration_Controls_Germany_Report

³⁸ http://ceaseval.eu/publications/28_WP4_Greece.pdf

decisions is conducted by staff from the Hellenic Police or the Armed forces, with the aim of concluding the asylum procedure within a 2-week time frame.

As of March 1st, 2020³⁹, the Government of Greece decided to suspend all new asylum applications introduced. The decision was justified with the extraordinary circumstances and the necessity to confront what is referred to as an “asymmetric threat to the national security”, which prevails over the application of EU law and international law regarding asylum procedures. The announcement also referred to a lack of capacity to process, within a reasonable period of time, asylum applications that would be submitted during the “illegal mass entry into the country”. All asylum applications by individuals “entering the country illegally will be suspended” and individuals will be returned, without registration to the country of departure or their country of origin.

This framing of asylum seekers as irregular migrants, and subsequently applying a different set of measures is similar to the approach used in non-European countries, including Tunisia, Algeria and Egypt. In Tunisia, the 2014 constitution provides for the right to seek asylum⁴⁰. However, the country does not have an asylum law. The issue of asylum seekers protection is a low priority for Tunisian policy makers, given other political challenges. Asylum seekers arriving to Tunisia irregularly are treated as irregular migrants, meaning criminal offenders, and are kept in detention and unable to reach the UNHCR to submit their asylum claim. There have been several reports of authorities deploying a strategy to stop irregular migrants from attempting to make asylum claims. Detention and “push-backs” at the borders are common practices, not only in Tunisia but in other North African countries as well.

3.1.2 Policies Addressing Irregular Migration

Policies addressing irregular migration are particularly relevant to understanding how policymakers address irregular movements, which threats they identify as resulting from migrants (irregularly) leaving their countries of origin and aspiring to arrive to particular countries of destination, and which aspects of migrants’ perceptions they identify as key in countering these threats. The policymakers’ response varies amongst countries of origin, transit and destination, with countries of origin and transit such as Tunisia, Algeria, and Egypt largely following a “cimmigration approach”, criminalizing irregular migrants, including asylum seekers. European countries with an external EU border such as Bulgaria, Italy and Greece, have strengthened their preventive measures through fencing policies, increased border capacities in coordination with Frontex, and promoted awareness campaigns deterring migrants from undertaking dangerous journeys to reach Europe. Countries considered to be predominantly of destination such as Belgium have also undertaken similar measures, in addition to implementing changes in laws and regulations facilitating the repatriation of irregularly-staying migrants, in particular those detained for crimes committed in European countries.

The repatriation of illegally staying criminals is outlined as an important priority for many European governments. In Belgium, convicted criminals who are staying in Belgium irregularly are transferred much more efficiently from their prison cells to deportation, which is linked to a stronger collaboration

³⁹<https://lawnet.gr/law-news/%CF%86%CE%B5%CE%BA-%CE%B145-2020-%CE%B1%CE%BD%CE%B1%CF%83%CF%84%CE%BF%CE%BB%CE%AE-%CF%84%CE%B7%CF%82-%CF%85%CF%80%CE%BF%CE%B2%CE%BF%CE%BB%CE%AE%CF%82-%CE%B1%CE%B9%CF%84%CE%AE%CF%83%CE%B5%CF%89/>

⁴⁰ <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s12134-018-0596-7>

with the Ministry of Justice. The result was an increase in the number of convicted criminals' deportations from 625 in 2017 to 1622 in 2017, with a total of more than 6,000 convicted criminals being deported over the last few years⁴¹.

In Bulgaria, a country of first entrance to the EU and protecting the Schengen border, irregular migration flows include both immediate inflows as well as returns from other EU Member States. . In reaction the sharp increase of illegal border crossings in 2015⁴² the return responses in countries further on the route (from Austria to Hungary, from Hungary to Serbia, from Serbia to Bulgaria) and the observed increasing smuggling activities supporting large groups of migrants crossing into the country, Bulgaria significantly increased its fencing policy by building up fences almost on the entire land border, with second and third lines of control at the green borders. In addition, the border police were reinforced with gendarmerie units, with the national army and seconded border guards from Frontex. The share of irregular migrants apprehended at the border and who were not registered into the Automated Fingerprint Identification System, when exiting Bulgaria, dropped from over 70% in first half of 2015 to less than 45% in the first half of 2016. At the same time however, the firsts months of the 2015 migration policy crises lead to increased smuggling activities at the Bulgarian southern borders of new criminal networks alongside the already established migrant smuggling networks. Alongside the General Directorate for Border Police other law enforcement institutions got involved in fighting migrant smuggling and smugglers as articles 280 and 281 of the Bulgarian Criminal Code stipulate penalties and fines for smugglers, with a list of aggravating circumstances, and confiscation of vehicles⁴³.

The non-EU countries Algeria and Tunisia are both countries of origin and countries of transit of irregular migration. Several international legal instruments address the right to leave one's country as a freedom that can be subjected to restrictions when necessary to protect national security, public order or morals, public health, and the rights and freedoms of others. Both Algeria and Tunisia punish the exit of the country through illegal means.

Overtime, Algeria has become a country of settlement for migrants who had intended to transit through the country, particularly, large numbers of sub-Saharan African migrants who are irregularly residing in Algeria, specifically in border regions, where they have been allegedly committing serious crimes that threaten the safety and security of citizens and the national economy. To this effect, Algeria has put in place legal, structural, and security measures as well as economic measures to counter irregular migration⁴⁴. The legal and structural measures emphasise the importance of enhancing the control over the migration flows heading towards its territory. The legal framework of this measure is the 2008 law regulating the conditions of entry, residence and movement of migrants in the country by expanding the scope of powers vested in the relevant authorities in charge of controlling the situation of foreigners and limiting the length of the visas issued. This is done, in addition to deportation, through *expulsion or push backs to the borders*, as well as criminal sentences including fines and imprisonment. Algeria not only criminalises any Algerian but also any foreign national who leaves the Algerian territory irregularly, using fraudulent identification documents, or any other deceiving means and withholding the use of official documents or going through the adequate process.

⁴¹ <https://www.dekamer.be/doc/FLWB/pdf/54/3296/54K3296021.pdf>

⁴² https://csd.bg/fileadmin/user_upload/publications_library/files/23264.pdf

⁴³ https://csd.bg/fileadmin/user_upload/publications_library/files/23264.pdf

⁴⁴ <https://www.asjp.cerist.dz/en/article/72404>

The punishment is either two to six months of imprisonment or a fine ranging from 20,000 to 60,000 Algerian dinars (the equivalent of 150 to 450 EUR)⁴⁵.

In addition, the General Directorate for National Security established the Central Office to combat irregular migration, which is the central body to conduct and coordinate between different regional entities to conduct investigations. The Algerian authorities have also put in place a regional team for the investigation of irregular migration, which was tasked to research, identify and follow irregular migration and migrant smuggling networks. Since the unrest witnessed by Tunisia and Libya over the last few years, Algeria became a country of transit and destination for migrants entering illegally. The European approach of securitising the borders and the comparatively stable economic situation led Algeria to become a destination for migrants originally aiming to reach European shores⁴⁶. To counter this perceived threat, the Algerian Government took steps to increase the monitoring of its borders and crossing points, and counter the employment of foreigners using fraudulent documents, involved in marriages of convenience or in *symbolic parenthood*. In addition, the state has banned hosting these migrants, or transporting them internally between governorates, all of which is reinforced through harsh punishments. The Algerian law regulating the movements of migrants to and from Algeria aims at addressing, among other perceived threats, “the influx of large waves of irregular migrants through the Southern borders, and the consequences of these movements such as the increase of organised crime, terrorism, deadly diseases, and informal economic activities”⁴⁷.

Also, Tunisia’s current migration policy is focused on preventing irregular migration. Since 1998, Tunisia was among the first countries, along with Morocco, to sign a readmission agreement with Italy. The promotion of legal pathways to migration has also been among the priorities promoted by various north African governments before and after the Arab Spring, often contrasting with policies discouraging and often criminalising, irregular migration⁴⁸. Under Tunisian law, Tunisian citizens who try to irregularly exit the country shall be punished through detention and the payment of a fine despite being unconstitutional (Article 24 of the 2014 constitution provides that every citizen has the right to leave the country). If Tunisians irregularly exit the country, they shall be punished upon return, with a 15-day to 6-month prison sentence and a fine of 30 to 120 Tunisian Dinars (Between 11 and 46 EUR). Although the law has not changed, the implementation of the law differs and practices before the 2011 uprisings saw more Tunisian citizens held in detention centers after being arrested for irregularly migrating from the country, while those arrested after 2011 were mostly released after paying a fine⁴⁹.

Another law criminalises migration-related activities (*since 1968*) stipulating that individuals who directly or indirectly help or attempt to facilitate the entry, exit, or stay of irregular migrants into the country will face a 1 month to 1 year prison sentence and a fine between 6 and 120 dinars (2.3 to 46 EUR). This law applies equally to migrant smugglers and volunteers providing aid to irregular migrants, and further enlarges the scope of the criminalisation of migration-related activities. The 2004 law introduced tougher sanctions on the activities mentioned in the previous law, with a prison sentence of 4 years and a fine of 10,000 Tunisian Dinars (about 3,800 EUR), to anyone sheltering or providing

⁴⁵ <https://www.asjp.cerist.dz/en/article/72404>

⁴⁶ <https://issafrica.org/iss-today/algerias-migration-policy-conundrum>

⁴⁷ <https://www.asjp.cerist.dz/en/article/72404>

⁴⁸ <https://cadmus.eui.eu/bitstream/handle/1814/33135/INTERACT-RR-2014%20-%202022.pdf?sequence=1>

⁴⁹ <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s12134-018-0596-7>

support or transportation or any other type of help. The law also criminalises the non-denouncement of irregular migrants and individuals helping them by sentencing those who, “even covered by the obligation of professional secrecy fail to immediately report”⁵⁰ any activities involving irregular migrants, with a 3-month prison sentence and a fine of 500 Tunisian Dinars (about 190 EUR).

From a European perspective, Tunisia is seen as a key partner in creating a pre-frontier buffer zone against irregular migration from Tunisian citizens seeking better lives in Europe as well as migrants from other African countries trying to reach Europe⁵¹. The EU has for long encouraged cooperation with Frontex in the area of collection and sharing of intelligence on migration flows from Tunisia to the EU. In 2013, a program entitled Seahorse Mediterranean Network, was created with the aim of establishing a communication network between North African countries (including Egypt, Tunisia, and Algeria) and EU countries on the exchange of information on irregular migration. Although Tunisia had been part of the network since its inception, significant pressure had to be created to convince the country to actively participate in the program⁵².

The alignment of the vision between the EU and Tunisia stems from both parties perceiving irregular migration as a potential security threat, or in some cases a terrorist threat. The fight against irregular migration has been justified through two EU narratives, one referring to the security risk and potential terrorist threat that irregular migrants pose and the other about associating the fight against irregular migration as a proxy for dismantling organised criminal groups involved in migrant smuggling and trafficking. These two narratives were shared by both pre-revolutionary and post-revolutionary Tunisian governments. New security threats resulting from the escalation of the war in Libya shifted the narratives of irregular migration movements to a focus on the “infiltration of terrorist groups through Libya”.

Yet another approach towards dealing with preventing and combating irregular migration to be highlighted here are campaigns like the Italian "Aware Migrants"⁵³ campaign, which was launched in July of 2016 by the Italian government in collaboration with IOM. The declared purpose of the campaign is to reduce the number of deaths in the Mediterranean Sea and it is directed at potential young migrants in various countries in West and North Africa. "Aware Migrants" aims to increase awareness among potential migrants focusing on the dangerousness of the irregular journey to reach Europe through the desert and the Mediterranean Sea. The descriptions of the risks, the story of the losses, of the violence suffered in the journey, of the disillusionment of expectations once they reach Europe, are told by migrants who managed to reach Italy. The campaign has been implemented using different communication channels, in particular a web site, a Facebook page, a Twitter account, Instagram and YouTube page. The website is specifically available in three languages: English, French and Arabic and includes mainly four sections: "stories", "news", "media" and "alternatives". In the first section there are video-stories, where migrants tell their experiences, highlighting the difficulties and abuses suffered. In the other sections there are: general news on migrations to Europe, alternative information channels through media, a list of opportunities in several African countries for the purpose

⁵⁰ <https://cadmus.eui.eu/bitstream/handle/1814/33135/INTERACT-RR-2014%20-%202022.pdf?sequence=1>

⁵¹ <https://cadmus.eui.eu/bitstream/handle/1814/33135/INTERACT-RR-2014%20-%202022.pdf?sequence=1>

⁵² <https://cadmus.eui.eu/bitstream/handle/1814/33135/INTERACT-RR-2014%20-%202022.pdf?sequence=1>

⁵³ <https://awaremigrants.org/>

of promoting valid alternatives to irregular migration in the country of origin and, finally, there is an information page about the appropriate procedures to legally enter selected European countries.

3.1.3 Border Control Policies

Border control policies vary greatly depending on the geographic position of countries and the threats partially linked to the physical borders. In order to understand border management policies, it is important to understand which functions, both symbolic and *physical*, borders are meant to fulfil. Anderson (1996) analyses borders both as an institution and a process. Borders as institutions are meant to represent the scope of state sovereignty and rights of citizens. Borders as a process, represent an instrument of state policy but also of national identity⁵⁴. Traditionally linked with the management and countering of irregular movements, new threats have been identified by policymakers, including the movements of legal migrants with a criminal background within the EU, the use of novel technologies such as drones and satellite maps by migrant smugglers, the constant shift of migrant routes to Europe, the undetected movements of individuals across the Schengen area, and the limited capacities and resources of third non-EU countries in border management. Unlike previous policies, border control policies require more cooperation across states and measures undertaken are often implemented in collaboration with different state institutions.

The security threats linked to migrants' behaviour within the EU has seen a change in bordering practices, where individual EU countries imposed new restrictions and checks to ensure the safety of their territories. In the context of European cooperation, many countries have been partaking in the *Eurescrim* project aimed at countering the movement of third country nationals holding residence permits issued by other European countries and who are involved in offenses against public safety. Since the project was launched 4 years ago, 134 individuals in Belgium have seen their residence permits (issued by another member state) terminated, which allowed Belgium to detain them in order to be deported to their countries of origin⁵⁵.

The issue of transit migration has been an increasing concern for the UK and its neighbouring countries and many initiatives were taken to address it. In 2016, the operation "Medusa" was initiated, with the goal of reinforcing the control of groups crossing in large numbers the Belgian border to reach the UK. The operation allowed to better identify these individuals and falls under a global scheme of combating human trafficking, human smuggling and *transit migration*. This initiative was undertaken in collaboration with the Royal Belgian Federation Carriers and logistical services providers (Febetra), the Public Federal Service of Interior Affairs (SPF Intérieur) and the Federal Police. As part of this initiative, the Office of Foreigners organised an information campaign targeting lorry drivers to draw their attention to the phenomenon of people illegally embarking in their lorries.

In federal states such as Germany, similar measures reinforcing border control were taken. The German executive policing powers fall under the states' authorities, with the exception of the federal Border Guard now called Federal Police. With the large scale of arrival of asylum seekers in 2015 and the ongoing debates of reinstating internal border controls, Germany has decided to carry out internal border checks. This new migration control has been carried out since then, justified under the relevant articles of the Schengen Borders Code, initially citing Article 25 (a threat to public policy and internal security) then Article 29 (exceptional circumstances putting the overall functioning of the area without

⁵⁴ Anderson, M. (1996). *Frontiers: territory and state formation in the modern world*. Cambridge, Polity Press.

⁵⁵ <https://www.dekamer.be/doc/FLWB/pdf/54/3296/54K3296021.pdf>

internal border controls at risk)⁵⁶. The extension of these border measures well after the peak of the so-called 2015 “Migration Crisis” reflects an understanding of potential threats as a constant, and calls for maintaining heightened measures such as border control with another EU state to counter what is seen as continuously “exceptional circumstances”.

The narrative of border control is seen as an essential element of integrated migration management strategy. Border control also applies to external borders, which translates into cooperation with third countries as well as securitizing the EU external borders. The process of working closely with third countries has been described as long, challenging and only evolving in small steps. As part of the Externalisation Strategy, Germany has introduced various measures, including the provision of resources to specific third countries around the EU, amongst which Tunisia and Egypt. This support includes police capacity-building and training, assistance in security sector reforms, counterterrorism, border management, and the provision of police, border security and military forces equipment⁵⁷.

To address irregular migration, Algeria has combined a legal and security-focused approach, following the example of other countries. The increased control at the borders was done through increasing the deployment of human resources and the enhancement of material means to control the border, surround the territory and protect it from any illegal crossings whether to enter or exit the territory. Forces of the border police have been deployed at all crossings⁵⁸.

To facilitate controls across the borders, the Algerian state emphasised the importance of creating biometric visas with neighbouring countries, particularly African countries. These visas would enable those working in border control centers from recognizing individuals holding identification documents and would become a deterrent to those using fraudulent documents. This measure also aims at introducing computerised procedures to track the entries and exits of any foreigner and to account for those residing illegally, in coordination with the local civil authorities across the country. In addition, the capacities of the coast guards were reinforced and the number of coast guard patrols was doubled. The technology used to guard the coast was also modernised and aerial monitoring was used to trace migration on land and at sea⁵⁹. The increased use and reliance on new technologies as well as the establishment of cooperation agreements with neighbouring countries adds to the efforts made by the Algerian state to increase its security capacities and has a deterrent effect on prospective migrants and migrant smugglers.

Egypt, on the other hand, adopted an “anti-human smuggling law” in 2016 and signed the Association Agreement with the EU in 2017. This led to an increase in border controls along the Egyptian shores⁶⁰, in the framework of a program titled “Enhancing the Response to Migration Challenges in Egypt” funded by the EU Emergency Trust Fund for Africa (EUTF). The terms of agreement between the EU and Egypt transcended the externalisation pattern seen with other countries and the conditionality attached to border management and return. Egypt’s border management capacities have been significantly upgraded, including the trainings of officials on border management and funding the National Coordinating Committee for Combating and Preventing Illegal Migration (NCCPIM). This

⁵⁶ https://www.academia.edu/39746749/Border_Management_and_Migration_Controls_Germany_Report

⁵⁷ https://www.academia.edu/39746749/Border_Management_and_Migration_Controls_Germany_Report

⁵⁸ <https://www.asjp.cerist.dz/en/article/72404>

⁵⁹ <https://www.asjp.cerist.dz/en/article/72404>

⁶⁰ <https://euromedrights.org/publication/eu-egypt-migration-cooperation-where-are-human-rights/>

upgrade has also included support to the counter-terrorism policy, and the establishing of cooperation between Frontex and Egyptian authorities with the exchange of intelligence⁶¹.

These agreements have been instrumental in strengthening third countries capacities at managing their borders but have also impacted migrants and smuggling networks behaviours. The technological lag, the introduction of new identification and travel documents, and the guarding of new crossing points, in combination with stricter sentences for those who do not comply have aimed at deterring migrants through a command and control approach.

3.1.4 Integration Policies

Anecdotal evidence has shown that integration policies contribute to prospective migrants' perceptions on destination countries. Investigating integration policies provides an important input in not only understanding their signalling role to migrants, but also how policymakers conceive of what makes a successful integration and which threats hamper this process and may create security concerns. In this section, we will look at policies at the regional (EU), national as well as federal level, since responsibilities lie with respective communities or states to define and implement an integration strategy.

Integration policies in Europe have growingly become more targeted, to address specific needs and challenges of particular groups, including refugees, third country nationals arriving to Europe for work purposes, as well as other subgroups. The further refinement of integration policies beyond the geographic and societal specificities of the contexts where migrants move reflects an understanding of the varying needs, challenges, and potential threats that could arise from the lack of integration of different groups. In addition, more efforts have been made to shift the integration process of prospective migrants to include countries of origin and transit as well as make use of novel technologies and social media to reach different migrant groups and provide reliable information on different topics.

The overarching policy on the integration of third country nationals in the European Union has developed in the last years in response to findings suggesting that third country citizens fare worse than their European counterparts in terms of employment, education and social inclusion⁶². Although this is not necessarily seen as an immediate security threat, the lack of integration of third country nationals can provide a breeding ground for a range of threats from lack of social cohesion in communities to radicalisation and criminal activities. In 2016, the EU developed an Action Plan on the integration of third-country nationals. This was partially motivated by findings pointing to the fact that, despite the efforts made to integrate third-country nationals, third country citizens face barriers in the education system, on the labour market and in accessing housing, which puts them at risk of poverty and social exclusion, even in cases where they are in employment⁶³.

⁶¹ <https://euromedrights.org/publication/eu-egypt-migration-cooperation-where-are-human-rights/>

⁶² https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/sites/homeaffairs/files/what-we-do/policies/european-agenda-migration/proposal-implementation-package/docs/20160607/communication_action_plan_integration_third-country_nationals_en.pdf

⁶³ https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/sites/homeaffairs/files/what-we-do/policies/european-agenda-migration/proposal-implementation-package/docs/20160607/communication_action_plan_integration_third-country_nationals_en.pdf

To overcome these shortcomings, the EU promoted more targeted integration policies, taking into consideration individual characteristics. Among the measures aimed at improving integration outcomes: pre-departure initiatives targeting refugees being resettled, or migrants joining their families in the EU or taking up jobs in Europe. Pre-departure language and job-targeted training significantly fast-track migrants' integration into their new environment. The programs are jointly designed by countries of origin or transit and countries of destination, which has proven to be particularly efficient at accelerating integration.

The use of technology and social media has the potential to improve integration. Technologies, social media and the internet are useful tools to fulfil migrants' needs in terms of integration at different stages of the process, including prior to their departure. Some Member States have already developed tools online, such as phone applications to inform newly-arrived asylum seekers about their rights, provide online basic language courses and practical information to facilitate access to different institutions and cater to different life needs. The EU also developed tools for coordination, funding and monitoring, including the monitoring of social inclusion and the active participation of third country nationals in society.

In specific contexts, countries have followed an approach that aims at enforcing integration measures and imposing sanctions where migrants fail to reach particular integration targets.

In Belgium, for instance, while policies related to immigration and asylum are a federal competence, integration policy falls under the responsibility of the three different language communities. In 2016, the Belgian Government introduced a new law, which includes a new residence condition to the Immigration Act, stipulating that certain non-EU foreigners intending to reside in Belgium need to provide evidence of their willingness to integrate into Belgian society to keep their residence permit⁶⁴. This entered into force in 2017. At the time of their residence application, non-EU foreigners are informed that their integration efforts will be controlled and reviewed at the first instance of renewal of their residence permits. The individual has the responsibility to provide proof of her/his integration efforts and the state has the right to put an end to their right to reside in Belgium if they deem that the foreigner did not make reasonable efforts to integrate.⁶⁵

A second part of the law aims to put in place a "newcomers' declaration" aimed at all newly arriving non-EU migrants, who would need to sign a declaration indicating that they understand their rights and obligations as well as the values and liberties of the Belgian society and that they will act in accordance with them⁶⁶. This declaration provides an example of integration policies increasingly becoming an enforceable process punishable by the withdrawal of the right to reside and work rather than an optional interactive process that allows for the inclusion of different cultural norms. Integration becomes a necessity for all migrants residing and working in Belgium to maintain their status or face expulsion. This law has been heavily criticised by different parties, especially where the state defers the interpretation of integration standards to different language communities. The contrast between the localised understanding of integration and the creation of obligations on

⁶⁴ <https://www.dekamer.be/doc/FLWB/pdf/54/2111/54K2111017.pdf>

⁶⁵ <https://www.dekamer.be/doc/FLWB/pdf/54/2111/54K2111017.pdf>

⁶⁶ https://www.rtbef.be/info/belgique/detail_la-declaration-des-primos-arrivants-peut-etre-uniquement-concretisee-en-flandre?id=9646355

migrants reflects a new understanding of policy measures as being both localised and essential for social cohesion.

By contrast, the integration policy for asylum seekers and refugees in Germany follows an incentive-based approach, where positive integration efforts are rewarded rather than punished. Under the Act to Accelerate Asylum Procedures, asylum seekers who are more likely to settle in Germany have access to integration courses, job-related language support, promotion of employment and the temporary lift of the employment ban⁶⁷. In the same period, the Act to Readjust the Right to Stay and Termination Residency introduced a new right of residency which is independent of age and without a deadline, in the case of “suitable integration”. Suitable integration is mostly linked to a language test corresponding to the A2 European level.

In addition to measures aimed at incentivising migrants to integrate through directly linking migration status to integration outcomes, some states specifically targeted external threats to integration, namely discrimination, social and political exclusion and different forms of hate speech. In the framework of the update of the Integrated Communities Strategy-Action Plan, the Government also published a refresh Hate Crime Action Plan, targeting anti-Semitism and anti-Muslim *actions* and supporting victims of these crimes. The Government has also taken active steps in driving integration at the local level, piloted in five integration areas, with each *Local Integration Partnership* identifying its own local priorities and the most effective ways to address them⁶⁸. The UK Government has also set up a Controlling Migration Fund of 26 million pounds aimed at supporting local projects across England in places where the scope of recent migration has affected local services and communities. The projects funded tackle a wide range of challenges including abusive landlords, migrant rough sleeping, social integration and building stronger communities⁶⁹. Similar initiatives were undertaken in Greece where the Government has created the National Monitoring and Evaluation Mechanism for Political Inclusion and Social Cohesion, as well as the National Council Against Racism and Intolerance to create and promote policies aimed at enhancing social inclusion and cohesion, and tackle racism and intolerance, in coordination with civil society organisations and other partners⁷⁰.

3.1.5 Return Policies

Examining return policies is particularly relevant to understanding governments’ responses to irregular migration and the dynamics between countries of origin, transit and destination. Although, as highlighted in previous sections, irregular migration itself is considered to be a security threat as well as a symbolic one, other associated threats partially linked with the vulnerabilities faced by irregular migrants such as exposure to exploitative informal economies and criminal networks have been included as a rationale behind improving return policies. Similar to border control policies, return policies rely on cooperation between states, which will be further explored in this section, in the context of incentivised cooperation and readmission agreements.

⁶⁷ https://www.academia.edu/39746749/Border_Management_and_Migration_Controls_Germany_Report

⁶⁸ https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/778045/Integrated_Communities_Strategy_Govt_Action_Plan.pdf

⁶⁹ https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/778045/Integrated_Communities_Strategy_Govt_Action_Plan.pdf

⁷⁰ http://www.opengov.gr/immigration/wp-content/uploads/downloads/2019/07/Εθνική-Στρατηγική-για-την-Ένταξη_final_.pdf

Return decisions are as measures to counter a host of threats, ranging from irregular migration to migrants' involvement in criminal activities. Increasingly, more countries have advocated for a repatriation of "undesirable" individuals posing a security threat to countries. In Belgium, the issue of incarcerated criminals with a residence status was addressed in the Policy Note from the State Secretary for Asylum and Migration for 2018-2019⁷¹. The reform of the law on Foreigners decreased the legal obstacles to withdrawing residence permits from convicted criminals. Under this new law, convicted migrant criminals face deportation at the end of their sentence. At the time of the publication of the Policy Note, 195 decisions of residence right termination were signed, in line with the new legislation. This entails that at the end of prison sentences, some migrants convicted for a crime will be deported to their countries of origin. The current administration underlined that they will make use of the new legislation – of "stripping criminals of residence rights status – as often as possible, for disrupting the public order"⁷². These measures applying to legal residents as well as irregular migrants outlines the weight put on the criminal involvement of migrants regardless of the migration status.

Algeria has implemented return policies putting in place procedures for individuals whose legal stay has expired and for those who would like to voluntarily return to their countries of origin. For the forced return, migrants are either taken towards the borders or forcibly removed. This is described as a procedure taken against migrants described as "undesirable individuals" and whose presence represents a threat to the public order and security, as well as for those individuals who have entered and/or resided in Algeria illegally. Return policies are described as a symbol of state sovereignty over a territory, and are implemented in line with the law⁷³.

In EU countries, voluntary return policies are also designed to incentivise migrants to return to their countries of origin through financial incentives and reintegration programs for asylum seekers and other migrants. Germany has several programmes combined with reintegration providing short term training and financial incentives on the federal and state level. Under the Reintegration and Emigration Programme for Asylum Seekers in Germany and the Government Assisted Repatriation Programme, 54,006 departures took place in 2016 and another 29,587 in 2017. Information centers based in reception camps also provide advice on voluntary returns. This counselling is carried out by the Federal Office for Migration and Refugees (BAMF), which is the same institution in charge of evaluating asylum applications⁷⁴. The provision of information on voluntary return pathways in reception centers and the provision of counselling on return by institutions in charge of asylum allows migrants to be exposed to information they would otherwise not have access to in their daily environment. The availability of these resources plays a role in influencing migrants decision-making and their assessment of voluntary return as an option.

Similar to other policy areas, return measures can also be a tool to signal a government's position to irregular migrants. In the State Strategy on Migration for Kosovo, the return policy is seen as an important and complementary tool to combating irregular migration and it is aimed at impacting

⁷¹ <https://www.dekamer.be/doc/FLWB/pdf/54/3296/54K3296021.pdf>

⁷² <https://www.dekamer.be/doc/FLWB/pdf/54/3296/54K3296021.pdf>

⁷³ <https://www.asjp.cerist.dz/en/article/72404>

⁷⁴ https://www.academia.edu/39746749/Border_Management_and_Migration_Controls_Germany_Report

irregular movements by “sending a clear message to potential migrants that respecting legal provisions is the only way to benefit from migration”⁷⁵.

3.1.6 Policies Addressing Trafficking in Human Beings

At least two policy narratives aim to explain and claim the issue of trafficking in human beings. On the one side there is the penal law approach. The UN Anti-Trafficking Protocol (the Palermo Protocol) introduced for the first time an international, general definition of trafficking. The Palermo Protocol is placed under the UN Convention against Organised Crime, whose main concern – organized crime – is by definition the object of activity of law enforcement authorities, charged with maintaining the order, and by extension the safety, of their jurisdictions. From this perspective, addressing trafficking in human beings subscribes to security approaches.

On the other side, trafficking is being claimed by the area of human rights, but also by other areas. Laczko & Danailova-Trainor⁷⁶ (2009) acknowledge, for instance, that “the definition of human trafficking is operationalised from different perspectives based on the primary research area – for example, labour, migration, criminal justice – [...] with each area conceptualising trafficking within its own domain. It is worth mentioning that THB has been framed, even before the internationally accepted definition from the Palermo Protocol, as being linked with migration (see Cyrus, 2015⁷⁷). While shortly after the Palermo Protocol the policy debates on THB, at least in the European context, concentrated on the characteristics and legal elements of trafficking as different than smuggling, in the years 2000s the focus shifted towards (extreme) exploitation. Another shift in anti-trafficking approaches has been from the main priority given to protecting victims to a priority given, at least in the EU context, to prevention of trafficking. The entire approach of addressing demand in the context of trafficking – based on Article 18 of Directive 2011/36/EU – subscribes to this shift.

One of the established approaches to address trafficking has been the adoption and implementation of anti-trafficking legislation at national level. The first difference within this approach, between the EU Member States and non-EU countries considered in this report, is that the EU MSs are bound by the European Directive 2011/36/EU on preventing and combating trafficking in human beings and protecting its victims. All current and former EU MS included in this report (Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Germany, Greece, Italy, Spain and the United Kingdom) put in place anti-trafficking legislation which transposes the EU Anti-Trafficking Directive⁷⁸.

⁷⁵ http://www.kryeministri-ks.net/repository/docs/STATE_STRATEGY_ON_MIRGRATION_ACTION_PLAN_2013-2018.pdf?_cf_chl_jschl_tk_=55c273dc25e9c4a1497ad58947ef1d75455d862b-1576502654-0-AStqzLOCFsaTo7dhgmC8aoK2H8qt50bpj2Z2C6xfysNPS5NG6G-lyooGo0MixZFPwsLZ64VqVFaZlWfT5sZG3FMnMIQcRwWU8yq2BqDgorELHtveHE-FGziYXSnTJXfZxjGeazAeLxnld_gg4U0W0HOkITMkFEGW4VfvsIDepDNouHNzQjAefR-Z90fHfi5ILHwyyLLtAv7PFaWNTWCXU-68JX_4_Ef0KOU0fAFnDjOL_WboJu45D1HR1Z7KHZhd-rJ92Qbtrr0SoEzSRVxJgO56_JM-IfEeNJLcszBGyyGQtXUsScalaNyK4g2j7pZm0_ZSxUJEodUNPt88AhLS9OuTXRGZztlwuiRF4e_d9ha4

⁷⁶ Laczko F. & Danailova-Trainor, G. (2009), Trafficking in Persons and Human Development: Towards a More Integrated Policy response. Human Development Research Paper 2009/51. http://hdr.undp.org/sites/default/files/hdrp_2009_51.pdf.

⁷⁷ https://www.demandat.eu/sites/default/files/DemandAT_WP2_Cyrus_October_2015_FINAL.pdf

⁷⁸ For an analysis on the transposition of the Directive 2011/36/EU see the Report from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council assessing the extent to which Member States have taken the necessary measures in order to comply with the Directive 2011/36/EU on preventing and combating trafficking in human beings and protecting its victims in accordance with Article 23(1), available: https://ec.europa.eu/anti-trafficking/sites/antitrafficking/files/report_on_member_states_compliance_with_directive_2011-36_en.pdf

Under the section on trafficking in the context of migration, the second report from the Commission on the progress made in the fight against trafficking in human beings (2018⁷⁹) notes that “Member States report on victims of trafficking found in asylum application systems and on organised criminal groups abusing asylum procedures. Member States also report traffickers requiring victims to apply for international protection in an attempt to regularise the victims’ status” (p. 5)⁸⁰.

From the non-EU members under research, Kosovo’s Strategy on Migration outlines a holistic approach to tackling different aspects of human trafficking by strengthening its measures aimed at preventing all forms of trafficking and re-trafficking, investigating and sentencing traffickers, implementing anti-corruption measures for police officers, prosecutors, judges and other officials involved. The approach also mentions conducting investigations in the framework of cooperation in the areas of data collection and analysis from the police as well as other institutions⁸¹. Anti-trafficking legislation is in place in Algeria, Egypt and Tunisia. Under Algerian Law⁸², human trafficking is criminalised and punishable of 3 to 5 years of imprisonment, and a fine ranging from 300,000 to 500,000 Algerian dinars (equivalent to 2,200 to 3,700 EUR). This crime has recently been classified as a felony in some cases, and punishments have been toughened to reach up to 10 years of imprisonment and 200,000 Algerian dinars as a fine. In Egypt, Law 64 of 2010 on combating THB “portrays migrants as victims and criminalises those who are complicit the trade in people with coercion and for the purpose of exploitation. The Law foresees prison sentences for us to 15 years or in some cases life, and a fine between 50000 and 200.000 Egyptian pounds or the amount of the profit of the crime, whichever is greater”⁸³ (p. 11). From the three North-African countries under research, Tunisia – a non-member state of the Council of Europe – was invited in 2018 to sign the CoE Convention against THB (invitation valid until February 2023)⁸⁴. According to a report published by the Institute for Security Studies⁸⁵, “The 2016 Tunisian law lays out robust sanctions, ranging from 10 to 15 years’ imprisonment”⁸⁶.

⁷⁹ https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/sites/homeaffairs/files/what-we-do/policies/european-agenda-security/20181204_com-2018-777-report_en.pdf

⁸⁰ In the same document the Commission states that “trafficking in human beings should be addressed in the context of migration taking into account new patterns such as disproportionate targeting of women and girls trafficked for the purpose of sexual exploitation. Efforts should continue to ensure that all victims are identified and provided with assistance and protection appropriate to their gender, age and the form of exploitation” (p.5).

⁸¹ http://www.kryeministri-ks.net/repository/docs/STATE_STRATEGY_ON_MIRGRATION_ACTION_PLAN_2013-2018.pdf?_cf_chl_jschl_tk_=55c273dc25e9c4a1497ad58947ef1d75455d862b-1576502654-0-AStqzLOCFsaTo7dhgmC8aoK2H8qt50bpj2Z2C6xfysNPS5NG6G-lyooGo0MixZFPwsLZ64VqVFaZIWfT5sZG3FMnMIQcRwWU8yq2BqDgorELHtveHE-FGziYXSnTJXfZxjGeazAeLxnld_gg4U0W0HOkITMkFEGW4VfvsIDepDNouHNzQjAefR-Z90fHfi5ILHwwyLLtAv7PFaWNTWCXU-68JX_4_Ef0KOU0fAFnDjOL_WboJu45D1HR1Z7KHZhd-rJ92Qbtrr0SoEzSRVxJgO56_JM-lfEeNjLcszBGyyGQtXUsScalaNyK4g2j7pZm0_ZSxUJEodUNPt88AhLS9OuTXRGZztlwuiRF4e_d9ha7

⁸² <https://www.asjp.cerist.dz/en/article/72404>

⁸³ <https://euromedrights.org/publication/eu-egypt-migration-cooperation-where-are-human-rights/>

⁸⁴ <https://rm.coe.int/CoERMPublicCommonSearchServices/DisplayDCTMContent?documentId=09000016806cac22>

⁸⁵ “The ISS is an African non-profit organisation with offices in South Africa, Kenya, Ethiopia and Senegal. Our work covers transnational crimes, migration, maritime security and development, peacekeeping, peacebuilding, crime prevention and criminal justice, and the analysis of conflict and governance” (<https://issafrica.org/about-us/how-we-work>).

⁸⁶ <https://issafrica.org/iss-today/tunisia-must-put-its-human-trafficking-laws-to-work>

For the purpose of this report, in addition to the national anti-trafficking legislation⁸⁷, we will refer to measures aimed at addressing the demand for goods or services provided through exploitation or trafficking in human beings. Measures implemented to address demand depend on the institutional system in place in a country, as well as the prevalent types of trafficking addressed through those measures.

According to the 2016 GRETA report on the compliance of Kosovo with the standards of the Council of Europe Convention on Action against Trafficking in Human Beings, “since 2010, the Ministry of Internal Affairs has organised every year in September and October an awareness-raising campaign against human trafficking under the slogan ‘Open your eyes’”⁸⁸. Information campaigns aimed at informing the general public, as well as targeted groups, including children and their parents, about the dangers of trafficking, including labour exploitation, forced begging and sexual exploitation were also conducted.

In January 2019, the Algerian Ministry of Solidarity, Family Affairs, and Status of Women initiated an awareness campaign to stop the use of children in begging networks. The government continued to operate three hotlines, which were operational 24 hours a day, and a public website to report abuse and other crimes, including potential human trafficking crimes⁸⁹.

In Egypt, the National Coordinating Committee for Combating and Preventing Illegal Migration (NCCPIM) – in charge with coordinating the anti-trafficking national policy – “distributed anti-trafficking informational booklets to migrant laborers and all Egyptian embassies and diplomats abroad. NCCPIM & TIP and the National Council of Women conducted a media campaign about the treatment of domestic workers, a population vulnerable to trafficking. Another worth noting approach is a microfinance system, programs for the empowerment of women workers, literacy and elimination of slums and has prepared awareness programs on the dangers and forms of human trafficking in addition to targeting the phenomenon of illegal migration⁹⁰

In Tunisia, demand for forced labour is addressed through a series of measures. “The labour inspectorate designated 25 labour inspectors and 24 social workers trained as specialized points of contact for child trafficking victims. To address fraudulent labour recruitment practices, the Agency for Placement Abroad in Private Establishments (EPPA), a governmental agency, filed complaints with the MOI against 17 private employers for cases of fraud, extortion, or unauthorized abuses of Tunisians employed abroad; it also took action against 30 private employers who recruited workers without proper registration with the EPPA. This demonstrated a slight increase from actions the government took against fraudulent recruitment practices in the previous reporting period. In July 2017, the government signed a memorandum of understanding with the ILO and the largest Tunisian labour and employers' unions to promote decent work in Tunisia for 2017-2022.”⁹¹

To sum up, countries under research have in place various measures to address trafficking in human beings – from penal legislation and capacity building to financial incentives and information campaigns

⁸⁷ Criminology studies argue that penal legislation, in addition to correction and removing the danger from society, have a preventive effect (Source). However, such detailed legal analysis falls beyond the scope of this report.

⁸⁸ <https://rm.coe.int/16806454cc>

⁸⁹ https://dz.usembassy.gov/wp-content/uploads/sites/236/2019-Trafficking_in_Persons_Report.pdf

⁹⁰ <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/REPS-03-2019-0029/full/html#sec26>

⁹¹ <https://www.refworld.org/docid/5b3e0a51a.html>

– measures which depend on the characteristics of trafficking addressed, the institutional setting addressing trafficking as well as the groups considered vulnerable to trafficking.

3.2 Security-Related Policies

Security-related policies, both in the public and private sphere, are not specific to migrants but rather affect populations within a territory. Although some migration policies clearly overlap with different aspects of public security such as border management and human trafficking, these policies affect predominantly migrants and have therefore been included in the previous chapter. In this chapter, the focus lies on security-related policies linked with migration, by disproportionately affecting migrant groups more than other groups, or through making provision targeting specifically migrants, such as criminality among migrant groups.

3.2.1 Policies Addressing Criminality among Migrants

Addressing criminality among migrants, particularly irregular migrants has been a priority for many governments. Where the threat to public security and illicit economic activities conducted migrants are clear, European states have put in place different types of measures to address these threats, sometimes indiscriminate of the severity of the criminal act.

One of the most recent policy notes issued by the Belgian Government also addressed petty crime among migrants, and more specifically incidents of shoplifting or pickpocketing committed by migrants⁹². For these types of offenders intercepted by the police, measures to quickly deport them are rather limited but remain a priority for the Government. The “Gaudi” initiatives targeting “thieves” residing irregularly in Belgium involve large scale raids and tend to be particularly efficient with the coordination of local and federal police on one side and the Office for Foreigners on the other. These types of operations piloted since 2014 have led to the arrest of 1,347 individuals in an irregular situation, with some being transferred to closed detention centers and a few ending up in prisons. These few migrants are usually deported at the end of their sentence⁹³.

A similar approach targeting migrants with a criminal background was implemented by the UK, which will be revised following Brexit, to submit all migrants, including EU citizens to the same measures as third country nationals. Under the new UK Immigration System, the UK Immigration Rules regarding the refusal of entry, permission to remain and deportation will apply to all individuals entering the UK, including EU citizens. This is seen as enhancing the UK’s ability to refuse entry or remove EU citizens seen as threats to the country on the basis of their conduct or previous criminality. These measures are meant to introduce consistency when dealing with potential threats and preventing any dangerous individuals from crossing the border⁹⁴.

Currently, under the existing EU rules, a person must represent “a genuine, present, and sufficiently serious threat before he or she can be deported”. The EU rules also do not specify what types of behaviour can result in the refusal of entry, exclusion or deportation of an EU citizen from the UK, as well as the length of imprisonment. By contrast, the current UK rules that non-EU citizens are subjected to are stricter and more specific. To improve the safety and security of the UK, following the

⁹² <https://www.dekamer.be/doc/FLWB/pdf/54/3296/54K3296021.pdf>

⁹³ <https://www.dekamer.be/doc/FLWB/pdf/54/3296/54K3296021.pdf>

⁹⁴ https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/766465/The-UKs-future-skills-based-immigration-system-print-ready.pdf

implementation period, the Government intends to extend the application of the non-EU criminality criteria to EU citizens both when crossing the borders as well as when residing in the UK. The same extension of rules will apply to deportation in regards to criminal acts committed in the UK.

Intelligence led enforcement of immigration laws and rules aims to tackle involvement with organized crime groups, fraud and deception such as the case of Operation Boromo⁹⁵, links to wider criminality as well as offences against migrants. Between April and December 2018, the Home Office Immigration Enforcement teams reported to have disrupted and dismantled 185 organised immigration crime groups.

3.2.2 Policies Addressing Violent Extremism and Radicalisation

Several terrorist attacks perpetrated by migrants or individuals from a migration background took place in European countries after 2015⁹⁶. Although the link between these incidents and the more recent migration influxes has yet to be established, debates around the relationship between migration and terrorist threats have intensified. Countries under study, both European and non-European have experienced this phenomenon to varying degrees. Looking at measures addressing violent extremism and radicalisation provides an overview of the different types of responses from governments, aimed at tackling violent extremism and preventing radicalisation. According to the Council of Europe's Parliamentary Assembly newly arrived migrants, as well as European citizens of migrant origin and diasporas, are particularly vulnerable individuals, subjected to discrimination and marginalisation in their host societies, which increases their vulnerability to extremist propaganda⁹⁷. Another factor for the recruitment of vulnerable migrants includes the rise of social media and the internet as a platform facilitating the radicalisation process. Recruiters have been known to use social media to target individuals personally online and communicate with them, given the convenience and the relative privacy of such medium⁹⁸.

According to a parliamentary report by the Council of Europe, many migrants reach Europe with a set of "misconceptions" spread through smugglers detailing unrealistic and spectacular pictures of European cities via social media, often used in an advertisement to target prospective migrants. Some recruiters use the opportunity of smuggling migrants to preach amongst refugees in refugee camps and mosques. According to a counter-extremist organisation, these recruiters tap into the frustrations created by a lengthy and often ineffective asylum system to provoke hatred towards the "*West and Western values*" and setting them to perpetrate terrorist attacks against Europeans.

The report also details a typology of migrants who are often vulnerable to such narratives or similar ones: Young people between 16 and 24 years old with a history of poor school performance, possibly a criminal record ranging from petty crimes to more serious offenses, without work experience and

⁹⁵ Refers to a crime group arranging sham marriages and committing tax, benefit and travel ticket fraud.

⁹⁶ <https://cis.org/Report/Terrorist-Migration-Over-European-Borders>

⁹⁷

<http://semantic-pace.net/tools/pdf.aspx?doc=aHR0cDovL2Fzc2VtYmx5LmNvZS5pbncveG1sL1hSZWYvWDJlURXLWV4dHluYXNwP2ZpbGVpZD0yNTA1NCZsYW5nPUVO&xsl=aHR0cDovL3NlbnWFudGljcGFjZS5uZXQvWHNsdC9QZGYvWFJlZi1XRc1BVC1YTUwYUERGlnhzbA==&xsltparams=ZmlsZWlkPT1MDUQ>

⁹⁸

<http://semantic-pace.net/tools/pdf.aspx?doc=aHR0cDovL2Fzc2VtYmx5LmNvZS5pbncveG1sL1hSZWYvWDJlURXLWV4dHluYXNwP2ZpbGVpZD0yNTA1NCZsYW5nPUVO&xsl=aHR0cDovL3NlbnWFudGljcGFjZS5uZXQvWHNsdC9QZGYvWFJlZi1XRc1BVC1YTUwYUERGlnhzbA==&xsltparams=ZmlsZWlkPT1MDUQ>

often characterised as “second generation migrants”⁹⁹. Other radicalisation factors include prisons and detention centers, which were described as “massive incubators for radicalisation”, economic and social exclusion of migrants, lack of resources in reception facilities for migrants, described as “organised in a chaotic way with minimal to no resources”, as well as the discrimination and segregation of migrants in European societies.

To counter these threats, several European countries have put in place mechanisms to prevent radicalisation and violent extremism, including Belgium, Germany, Italy, Spain, and the UK. In Belgium, working groups were created within different government institutions. They specialise in particular trends or issues, including radicalisation online, on the radio, television, as well as right- and left-wing extremism, including salafism. This approach is complementary to other ad-hoc working groups who target what is referred to as “problematic radicalisation” which include “Hate Preachers”, “Mosques”, “Asylum and Migration”¹⁰⁰.

Similar to many countries facing hate preachers in mosques, Belgium introduced a set of reforms to combat hate preachers and ensure hate speech does not occur in places of worship. An additional control is also planned for visa applicants by imams from outside the EU. The visa assessment is no longer conducted solely by the national security but also involves the General Service for Intelligence and Security. The 2017 Policy Note highlights that only imams officially recognised and working in official mosques will be eligible for a visa¹⁰¹. In addition, under the Action Plan for the Prevention of Radicalisation Processes that Can Lead to Extremism and Terrorism, the Flemish Minister for Local and Provincial Government emphasises the importance of consulting with representatives of “philosophies of life” to facilitate interfaith dialogue as well as develop social orientation and Dutch as a second language training offer tailored to Imams. This project is piloted by the Agency for Integration and Civic Integration and is developed to be integrated within existing imam training. The Ministry of Integration also aims at facilitating the training and professionalisation of imams through the creation of educational and professional opportunities in collaboration with KU Leuven and the Antwerp University Association (AUHA)¹⁰². While some might see these measures as interference of the state in religious affairs, these interventions are not unique to Belgium and provide a new understanding of state and religious affairs dynamics under the “securitization of migration”.

These challenges are not unique to EU countries. Kosovo reports that among the pull factors mentioned in the context of violent radicalisation the influence of radical leaders, including imams with radical tendencies have played a central role in the recruitment of foreign fighters, as well as online radicalism with the rise of social media platforms such as YouTube, Facebook, Twitter, and other networks¹⁰³.

To counter these threats, the Strategy on Prevention of Violent Extremism and Radicalisation Leading to Terrorism mentions *four strategic objectives* ranging from early detection, prevention, intervention to de-radicalisation and reintegration. In addition, a commission was established to review the

⁹⁹ This term is misleading since they are not migrants but rather born to migrant parents.

¹⁰⁰ <https://www.dekamer.be/FLWB/PDF/54/1428/54K1428019.pdf>

¹⁰¹ <https://www.dekamer.be/doc/FLWB/pdf/54/2111/54K2111017.pdf>

¹⁰² https://www.fdfa.be/sites/default/files/atoms/files/actieplan_radicalisering_eng.pdf

¹⁰³ http://www.kryeministri-ks.net/repository/docs/STRATEGY_parandalim_-_ENG.pdf

religious content on the internet, as well as ensuring the translation of moderate religious content online in Albanian, coordinated by religious communities, government officials as well as field experts who are tasked to analyse existing religious content online¹⁰⁴. The creation of translated moderate counternarratives online represents a reactive intervention to online radicalisation that can serve as an example of more broadly countering false narratives leading to security threats.

3.3 Technology, Social Media and Information Policies

3.3.1 ICT Policies

The creation of joint databases between different institutions and ministries has been a key measure at utilising technology to counter threats stemming from lack of information, in relation to migrants' criminal backgrounds, and whether individuals represent a threat to public security. Measures involving a unified database were implemented in Germany and Belgium, and have had a significantly positive impact in bridging the gap and identifying potentially dangerous individuals.

In Belgium, an agreement between the Federal Police and the Office for Foreigners was elaborated, followed by the technical development of a National General Database (BNG). The Federal Police has access to and is able to consult the Database. As a result, the Office for Foreigners is able to verify if a foreigner committed actions affecting the public order and taking that into consideration when making an administrative decision. Prior to this procedure, the decision of the Office of Foreigners depended on the direct transfer of information by the police. As of 2018¹⁰⁵, the Office for Foreigners had direct access to the National General Database (BNG)¹⁰⁶. In total, 12,500 consultations were made by the Office for Foreigners during 2017, of which 3,129 yielded a positive result. In other terms, one out of 4 foreigners for which the Office made a background check through the database was known by the police authorities. These background findings were also taken into account when making and justifying a decision, as well as determining the duration of an entry ban¹⁰⁷.

Similarly in Germany, the Act to Improve the Exchange of Data was introduced in February 2016 to improve the existing data in the Central Register of Foreign Nationals (AZR)¹⁰⁸. The new database includes, in addition to information on foreigners' visas residing in Germany, the data of asylum and protection seekers. The information contains basic personal and identification information. The Act also provided for mandatory security checks on asylum seekers and the obligation to transmit data to the Central Register of Foreign Nationals on all authorities, conditional on the fact that they are authorised to do so. Previously, the Central Register of Foreign Nationals was operated by the Federal Office for Migration and Refugees (BAMF) in cooperation with the Federal Office of Administration and the Federal Criminal Police Office (BKA), mainly for the use of civil servants in the Foreigners' Offices across Germany. Access was also granted to police and customs authorities.

¹⁰⁴ http://www.kryeministri-ks.net/repository/docs/STRATEGY_parandalim_-_ENG.pdf

¹⁰⁵ <https://www.dekamer.be/doc/FLWB/pdf/54/3296/54K3296021.pdf>

¹⁰⁶ Banque de Données Nationale Générale

¹⁰⁷ <https://www.dekamer.be/doc/FLWB/pdf/54/3296/54K3296021.pdf>

¹⁰⁸ https://www.academia.edu/39746749/Border_Management_and_Migration_Controls_Germany_Report

3.3.2 Information Policies

Information campaigns have been instrumental in “rectifying” narratives of life in Europe and providing counternarratives to prospective migrants undertaking dangerous journeys to reach Europe. Information campaigns have also been utilised to address other challenges, such as ensuring the integration of newly arrived migrants to the UK, understanding asylum rights and procedures for Asylum seekers from safe countries of origin and creating awareness around vulnerable groups.

In order to manage new migrants’ expectations and prepare them for life in the UK, the Integrated Communities Strategy Action Plan launched in February 2019¹⁰⁹, the Government provides information for all visa application routes about what life in modern Britain is like, in order to bring awareness of what those values mean before individuals arrive¹¹⁰. An Integration Area Programme offers a package of practical information to newly arrived migrants to support their access and use of local services, as well as their effort to build social connections within their new communities.

Information campaigns have also been used to deter migrants and asylum seekers from reaching specific countries through social media platforms. In Belgium, the Government emphasised that dissuasion campaigns will be intensified and multiplied to convince potential victims of human trafficking not to go to Belgium. Social media platforms were used to inform specific nationalities, through targeted messages about the strict measures taken by the Belgian Government. This was part of a larger campaign aimed at tackling secondary movements among migrants in transit. The campaign also aimed at better informing migrants in transit about asylum procedures and the possible venues of asylum applications.

The Office of Foreigners initiated the action plan developed and had developed Facebook ads to dissuade migrants from undertaking the journey to Belgium. This allowed the targeting features of Facebook to reach specific audiences through these ads. Some advertisements have been communicated in 6 different languages (Arabic, Urdu, Kurdish, English, Hindi, and Pashto) in different locations in Belgium and Europe (Parc Maximilien, Zeebrugge, highway parkings, as well as “hotspots” in Greece and Italy, Northern France, Spanish “enclaves”, asylum centers in Germany). According to the report, these ads were consulted 776,538 times already¹¹¹.

In Germany, several initiatives on providing alternative views to how life in Europe is portrayed were conducted. The Federal Network African Diaspora of Germany, the Federal Foreign Service, as well as 6 of the top 10 African countries of origin for migrants in Germany launched “Lost Dreams”, a film project aimed to raise awareness and prevent loss of migrants’ lives and the exposure to dangers encountered on the way to Europe¹¹². The film project highlights the types of dangers migrants might encounter along the different smuggling routes across the Mediterranean, correct inaccurate information about Europe and Germany spread by smugglers to lure and convince migrants to undertake the dangerous journeys. The film project tries to correct the utopian image spread about

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https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/778045/Integrated_Communities_Strategy_Govt_Action_Plan.pdf

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https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/778045/Integrated_Communities_Strategy_Govt_Action_Plan.pdf

¹¹¹ <https://www.dekamer.be/doc/FLWB/pdf/54/3296/54K3296021.pdf>

¹¹² <http://lost-dreams.tang-ev.de/en/project-eng>

Germany as the land in which “milk and honey flow and money grows on trees” and is translated into German, French, English, Somali, and Hausa. This project aims at targeting mostly aspiring migrants in Somalia, Nigeria, Mali, Niger, Cameroon and DRC and is expected to have reached at least 15 million African viewers. The “Lost Dreams” project is based on real life experiences and features interviews with refugees from African countries who have taken the journey to Europe through the Mediterranean routes. Migrants are asked about *false* rumours circulated across Germany. Some celebrities of African descent in Germany also feature in these films with the aim of sending a message to African youth and warn them about the dangers of crossing the Mediterranean. Alternative legal ways of entering Germany are presented in the movies. The newly arrived refugees are interviewed in cooperation with partners in Italy and Spain along the coasts¹¹³.

3.4 Selected Types of Policy Measures – Discussion

This section outlines main arguments of selected policy measures identified in countries under study as addressing threats that are linked with perceptions. The types of policies collected are rather snapshots of policy measures’ mechanisms. While these measures operate within mutable contexts, a discussion on the relevance of such contexts, although necessary for a full policy analysis as well as an impact evaluation, falls beyond the scope of this report. As mentioned in the first chapter, this report is a starting point and a basis for the upcoming field work in countries under research, in the framework of the H2020 PERCEPTIONS project. The upcoming field work will focus, among others, on how policy makers and first-line practitioners understand the role of “perceptions of destination areas” in the decision-making process of migrants, including prospective migrants.

As outlined in the framework of analysis chapter of this report, the rising securitization of migration, particularly in Europe but also in some third countries included in this research, has shaped the common understanding of what or who represents a potential threat, as well as a more defensive and strict approach informing the policymaking in a number of EU and non-EU countries. The securitisation of migration has been a growing trend over the last decade, often described as a process of “repositioning areas of regular politics into the realm of security by increasingly using narratives of threat and danger aimed at justifying the adoption of extraordinary measures”¹¹⁴. Under the securitisation framework, measures, policies or operations that were once perceived as extreme, unjustified and inhumane become normalised. Looking at different areas of migration policies, ranging from asylum, settlement, integration and return, it becomes clear that the securitisation approach applies to different stages of migration journeys.

3.4.1 Policy Measures in the Area of Asylum

In the area of asylum policies, large influx of migrants has been framed (by policymakers) as a threat to countries’ stability and capacity to host asylum seekers. One manifestation of this threat has been detected as “abusive” practices, such as multiple asylum claims, which take up state resources and are aimed at prolonging the “abusive” asylum claimants’ residence in the country (while these multiple claims are being processed). To counter this threat, several countries (such as Belgium and Germany) introduced measures aimed at speeding the processing of processing asylum claims and reducing the costs of processing these claims. These changes in the procedures, while aimed to protect the asylum

¹¹³ <http://lost-dreams.tang-ev.de/en/project-eng>

¹¹⁴ <http://www.mixedmigration.org/articles/the-ever-rising-securitisation-of-mixed-migration/>

system (and its resources) from too many claims at once and from “false” claims aim, by extension, to also deter potential asylum seekers. This is clearly exemplified through additional measures in Germany, when the 2015 Act to Accelerate Asylum Procedures was introduced. The Act aimed at reducing the incentive of unjustified applications by replacing cash benefits with in-kind benefits during the initial reception phase, reducing the benefits for those who have to leave the country, and excluding asylum seekers from safe countries of origin from employment. In the typology of regulatory mechanisms introduced earlier in this report, these types of measures subscribe to command and control – changes in legislations – coupled with market-based approaches – financial disincentives – and aim at changing prospective asylum seekers’ behaviour through altering the migration infrastructure as a precipitating factor in the country of destination (see Van Hear, Bakewell and Long, 2017¹¹⁵). Another example of such mechanism, aimed at changing migration infrastructures, is the hotspot approach introduced by the European Commission to support frontline member states, like Greece, in order to alleviate the pressure and provide operational assistance to identify, register, fingerprint, and debrief newly arriving migrants and asylum seekers, as well as support return operations.

The Tunisian approach, where asylum seekers arriving to Tunisia irregularly are treated as irregular migrants – meaning offenders – and are kept in detention is another example of command and control. The message in this particular case is straightforward – those who do not comply with the law (and enter the country illegally) are sanctioned. Furthermore, those in detention are not able to reach UNHCR in order to submit their asylum claims, which is a strong disincentive for prospective asylum seekers.

3.4.2 Measures Addressing Irregular Migration

Irregular migration is regarded, from the perspective of a state, as a security threat to the territory of the country and to its sovereignty. States’ policies responses to irregular migration can be categorised in gatekeeping and fencing policies, along two dimensions – external (from the perspective of entering the country) and internal (with regard to the residency in the country) (see Vogel, 2016¹¹⁶). Gatekeeping measures have the goal to check eligibility for access to the territory or other rights that come with accessing a territory. From a gatekeeping perspective, measures on the external dimension are visa procedures and border controls at ports of entry, while measures on the internal dimension manifest as procedures to prevent access to legal status, labour market or welfare support. Fencing approaches have the aim to stop irregular migration from occurring. On the external dimension, fencing approaches are border controls outside ports of entry, while within the territory fencing manifests as police and labour market inspections.

Examples of measures presented in this report are various combinations of fencing and gate-keeping approaches. It is worth mentioning also that policymakers’ response varies amongst countries of origin, transit and destination. Countries of origin and transit, such as Tunisia or Algeria follow a what was called “crimmigration approach” – criminalizing irregular migrants, including asylum seekers. This particular approach, a command and control type of approach, falls under the internal dimension of gate-keeping measures. European countries with an external EU border, such as Bulgaria, Italy and

¹¹⁵ Push-pull: reconsidering the drivers of migration

¹¹⁶http://www.fb12.uni-bremen.de/fileadmin/Arbeitsgebiete/interkult/Vogel/2016_Vogel_migrationcontrol_wberen532.pdf

Greece, have strengthened their fencing policies, increased border capacities in coordination with Frontex, and promoted awareness campaigns deterring migrants from undertaking dangerous journeys to reach Europe. These measures, aiming at preventing irregular migration, address the external dimension of fencing policies. From the perspective of regulatory mechanisms, these measures (in countries at the EU external border) are combinations of command and control and market-based approaches¹¹⁷, particularly if they involve information campaigns that offer alternatives to irregular migration.

Information campaigns have been implemented in various policy areas, including policies addressing irregular migration. The declared goal of the 2016 “Aware Migrants”¹¹⁸ campaign was to reduce the number of deaths in the Mediterranean. According to its intervention logic, this campaign aims at reaching its goal through increasing awareness among prospective migrants with regard to the dangers of an irregular journey to Europe. Among the messages communicated in the framework of this campaign are messages from migrants who managed to reach Italy. They describe the risks they faced, the stories of their losses and the violence they suffered along the journey, as well as the disillusionment of their expectations once they reach Europe. The transmission of such messages constitutes perhaps the most straightforward example of measures aiming to address perceptions of migrants. One of the underlying assumptions of such information campaigns, aiming to discourage irregular migration (through messages on the danger of the journey) is that (potential) migrants held beliefs, which stand in contrast to knowledge¹¹⁹ (Pritchard, 2010¹²⁰). The underlying argument of these campaigns is that “what is presented to [potential migrants] in perceptual experience [e.g. images of Europe posted on social media platforms by smugglers to advertise their smuggling services] is not the world itself but merely an expression of the world from which [migrants] draw inferences about how the world [...] is” (Pritchard, 2010: 71¹²¹). Previous analyses of the intervention logic of information campaigns underlined the fact that “raising awareness is not sufficient if the campaign ultimately seeks to change behaviour” (Cyrus and Vogel, 2017: 22¹²²).

However, in addition to information about the dangers of an irregular journey to Europe, “Aware Migrants” provides information on alternatives, such as websites for finding legal employment either in African countries (such as Tunisia) or in European countries (particularly Germany). While this has the potential to change behaviour – in that prospective migrants choose these legal pathways instead of embarking on an irregular journey to Europe – the lack of information (available for this report) on

¹¹⁷ See further below in this chapter a discussion on information campaigns, subscribing to these approaches.

¹¹⁸ <https://awaremigrants.org/>

¹¹⁹ For the purpose of this analysis, knowledge here is understood as propositional knowledge – which refers to gathering (accurate) information about the world or about a specific situation (in this particular case, accurate information about the journey to Europe or to a particular country). Information and communication technologies contribute to what has been labelled as “the problem of perceptual knowledge”, since “the way things look isn’t always the way things are; appearances can be deceptive” (Pritchard, 2010: 69).

¹²⁰ Pritchard, D. (2010), *What is this thing called knowledge?* London and New York: Routledge

¹²¹ In the epistemology of knowledge this argument subscribes to indirect realism, according to which “there is an objective world out there, one that is independent of our experience of it – that is the ‘realism’ part – but that we can only know this world indirectly through experience” (Idem: 77).

¹²² https://www.demandat.eu/sites/default/files/DemandAT_WP9_Cyrus-Vogel_Campaigns_June%202017.pdf

the causal link between the information campaign and the reduction of irregular departures makes it difficult to analyse its impacts¹²³.

3.4.3 Measures in the Area of Border Control

With regard to border control, measures employed overlap, to a certain extent, with measures subscribing to fencing approaches aimed at stopping irregular migration. Threats and challenges addressed through measures subscribing to border management comprise: migrant smuggling, movements within the EU of regularly residing migrants and who have a criminal background, as well as the limited capacities and resources of third countries in border management. One measure employed was to change the regulations for border crossing. Germany, like other several Schengen countries, re-introduced border checks in the Schengen area, invoking the “exceptional circumstances” of the 2015 crisis. Such measures aimed at stopping migrants from entering the country and, in case of transit countries, determined migrants to choose alternative routes.

Border management, particularly through what was called externalisation of border control, is implemented through cooperation between countries’ homologue institutions. Along this line, Germany introduced various measures, including the provision of resources to specific third countries, amongst which Tunisia and Egypt. This support includes police capacity-building and training, assistance in security sector reforms and counterterrorism, among others¹²⁴. Agreements between the EU and third countries (such as the Association Agreement with the EU signed with Egypt in 2017), have been instrumental in strengthening third countries capacities at managing their borders but have also impacted migrants and smuggling networks behaviours. The introduction of new identification and travel documents, and the guarding of new crossing points, in combination with stricter sentences for those who do not comply have aimed at deterring migrants through a command and control approach.

3.4.4 Migration Integration Measures

Anecdotal evidence has shown that integration policies contribute to the creation of perceptions of countries of destination from prospective migrants’ perspectives. The overarching policy on the integration of third country nationals in the European Union has developed in the last years in response to findings suggesting that third country citizens fare worse than their European counterparts in terms of employment, education and social inclusion¹²⁵. Although this is not necessarily seen as an immediate security threat, the lack of integration of third country nationals can provide a breeding ground for a range of threats from lack of social cohesion in communities to radicalisation and criminal activities. Two approaches are relevant, from the perspective of mechanisms employed. In 2016, the Belgian Government introduced a new law, which includes a new residence condition to the Immigration Act, stipulating that certain non-EU foreigners intending to reside in Belgium need to provide evidence of

¹²³ An analysis of the impact of measures falls outside the scope of this report. In the framework of the PERCEPTIONS project, a separate report on “good practices” in addressing threats that are linked with perceptions is being compiled. Together – information on policy measures mechanisms, threats that are linked with perceptions and good practices in addressing these threats – form the basis for the upcoming field work in the framework of PERCEPTIONS.

¹²⁴ https://www.academia.edu/39746749/Border_Management_and_Migration_Controls_Germany_Report

¹²⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/sites/homeaffairs/files/what-we-do/policies/european-agenda-migration/proposal-implementation-package/docs/20160607/communication_action_plan_integration_third-country_nationals_en.pdf

their willingness to integrate into Belgian society to keep their residence permit¹²⁶. From this perspective, it is the migrant's responsibility to proof integration efforts and the regional administration can decide whether the migrant made reasonable efforts to integrate or not. In Germany, the integration policy for asylum seekers and refugees in Germany follows an incentive-based approach, where integration efforts are rewarded rather than the lack of such efforts being punished. These two approaches, while they both subscribe to command and control (being implemented through legal changes) employ different mechanisms for changing behaviour. The German approach would also subscribe, to a certain extent, to market-based approaches, as services offered to migrants legally residing in the country are being transformed into incentives for integration efforts.

3.4.5 Return Measures

Return decisions are measures to counter various threats, ranging from irregular migration to migrants' involvement in criminal activities. In Belgium, for instance, convicted migrant criminals (even if legally residing in Belgium) face deportation at the end of their sentence. This measure, different than criminal justice applied in case of Belgian citizens, implies that migrants with a criminal record continue to be regarded as a threat – “disrupting the public order”¹²⁷ – even after they serve their time. Subscribing to the command and control type of measure, this measure implies that, particularly in case of migrants, law enforcement approaches cannot have a correction and re-education effect. In so doing, it also signals that criminal behaviour among migrants will be stronger sanctioned (than in case of citizens). In EU countries, voluntary return policies are also designed to incentivise migrants to return to their countries of origin through financial incentives and reintegration programs for asylum seekers and other migrants. Germany has several programmes combined with reintegration providing short term training and financial incentives on the federal and state level.

3.4.6 Measures Addressing Trafficking in Human Beings

Traditionally, trafficking in human beings is being addressed through anti-trafficking legislations. All countries referred to in this report have legal provision in this sense. From the types of mechanisms employed in this policy area, it is worth mentioning – in addition to command and control – combined approaches aimed at addressing demand for goods or services that are produced or offered through exploitation or trafficking in human beings. This is the case of campaigns aimed at informing vulnerable groups about the dangers of illegal employment (such as the campaign in Egypt), but also sanctions applied to employers who engage in exploitative practices (such as the measures implemented in Tunisia).

Previous research on information campaigns aimed at reducing trafficking in human beings underlines the importance of this type of approach in anti-trafficking policies (Cyrus and Vogel, 2017¹²⁸). An analysis of the intervention logic of demand-side campaigns¹²⁹, particularly campaigns that address

¹²⁶ <https://www.dekamer.be/doc/FLWB/pdf/54/2111/54K2111017.pdf>

¹²⁷ <https://www.dekamer.be/doc/FLWB/pdf/54/3296/54K3296021.pdf>

¹²⁸ https://www.demandat.eu/sites/default/files/DemandAT_WP9_Cyrus-Vogel_Campaigns_June%202017.pdf

¹²⁹ Demand-side campaigns are aimed at reducing the demand for goods or services produced through exploitation or trafficking in human beings. The mentioned analysis looks at campaigns that address people as consumers who knowingly or unknowingly pay for the work or services of trafficked persons and campaigns that address the general public (who are expected to observe potential exploitative situations and report it to a hotline).

people as consumers who knowingly or unknowingly pay for the work or services of trafficked persons and campaigns that address the general public (who are expected to observe potential exploitative situations), showed that, in order to reach their intended goal, a quite long chain of effects has to be implemented in an uninterrupted way. “An interruption of the chain at any point means that the campaign has no impact on trafficking via the behaviour of the target group. Defects at any stage will water down the final impact on trafficking in human beings” (Cyrus and Vogel, 2017: 2¹³⁰). When it comes to information campaigns targeting the general public, such as the campaigns run in Kosovo for informing the public about the dangers of various types of trafficking, the aim is to change the public’s perception about the prevalence of exploitation in various areas (such as begging). As in the case of campaigns aiming to reduce irregular migration, perceptions (in the sense of ideas and information about a topic) are being addressed as an intermediary step. The intervention logic of such campaigns includes an assumed link between perceptions and actual behaviour, in the sense that campaigns assume that a change in perceptions will eventually lead to changes in behaviour.

¹³⁰ https://www.demandat.eu/sites/default/files/DemandAT_WP9_Cyrus-Vogel_Campaigns_June%202017.pdf

4 Conclusion

The “Securitization of migration”, understood as increasingly framing migration policies in the realm of security, has significantly expanded over the last five years. Narratives of threats and security risks have justified measures, policies, and laws that were once considered to be “extreme”. This report has shown that threats, as understood by states, are not only understood as public or individual security threats. Several institutions referred to economic threats resulting from a “disproportionate” number of asylum seekers arriving in countries of transit and destination, or migrants engaging in informal economic activities. Other threats, for example, symbolic threats to a country’s sovereignty by undermining its borders or abusing its policies have also been highlighted.

The policy measures introduced to counter these threats reflect an approach that not only aims at addressing particular challenges but also the behaviour, and sometimes environment, that gives rise to these challenges. Policies on addressing radicalisation online or the spread of disinformation on social media platforms signals states’ varying levels of intervention. However, what many of these policies had in common is a command and control approach, which manifests through the increasing involvement of law enforcement authorities at different stages of migration phases, the emphasis put on the collection and sharing of information on migrants across institutions and states, and the stricter methods used to enforce compliance, both in relation to neighbouring states as well as individuals. Governments have actively used incentives and disincentives to motivate migrants to integrate, comply, and make decisions on their return or asylum applications. Similar approaches have also been used by EU governments with countries of transit and origin, particularly regarding policies on return and border management, both of which require collaboration between these countries in order to address, for instance, irregular migration.

Looking at policy measures addressing a range of threats through the migration behaviour they intend to change serves as a foundation to understanding to what extent perceptions held by migrants are relevant for such policy measures.

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